

Forside

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The effect on fermentation of faba bean matrices with selected bacteria and yeast on production of organic acids and degradation of antinutrients.

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Abstract

Faba beans have become an increasingly popular sustainable source of plant-based protein. However, their nutritional value and digestibility are limited due to the presence of antinutritional factors (ANFs), including phytic acid, raffinose-family oligosaccharides (RFOs), vicine, and convicine.

This thesis sought to explore the potential for reducing ANFs through fermentation of a simulated faba bean substrate containing 7% faba bean protein concentrate, 1% glucose, and 1% sucrose. Fermentation was carried out using monocultures of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (*S. cerevisiae*), *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* (*L. plantarum*) and *Bacillus subtilis* natto (*B. subtilis* natto). Microbial growth was monitored at 0, 6, 24, and 48 hours at 30°C using blue-cap fermentations to assess whether these microorganisms can grow in faba bean matrices. The maximum cell counts reached $(1.64 \pm 0.08) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL for *S. cerevisiae*, $(7.75 \pm 0.25) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL for *L. plantarum*, and $(2.00 \pm 0.25) \times 10^6$ CFU/mL for *B. subtilis* natto within 48 hours. Notably, *B. subtilis* natto exhibited a 10-fold reduction in cell count at within the first 6 hours of fermentation.

Additionally, the potential for shelf-life enhancement through the production of antimicrobial compounds, specifically organic acids, was assessed. This was done by monitoring pH levels and analyzing organic acid production via HPLC throughout fermentation. The pH decreased significantly to 4.05 ± 0.00 for *L. plantarum* and 5.30 ± 0.01 for *S. cerevisiae* in the stationary growth phases. In contrast, *B. subtilis* natto exhibited no significant pH reduction, reaching a final pH of 5.56 ± 0.02 .

Acetic, lactic, and citric acid concentrations were measured throughout the fermentation period. Both *B. subtilis* natto and *S. cerevisiae* produced acetic acid, with *S. cerevisiae* producing 1.78 ± 0.26 g/kg after 24 hours, though it later consumed the acetic acid along with citric acid. *B. subtilis* natto produced 1.17 ± 0.04 g/kg acetic acid after 48 hours. Meanwhile, *L. plantarum* produced significant amounts of lactic acid during the stationary growth phase, producing 5.04 ± 0.01 g/kg.

Both *L. plantarum* and *S. cerevisiae* metabolized raffinose through fermentative metabolism, but *S. cerevisiae* was unable to assimilate it. Results for *B. subtilis* natto regarding raffinose utilization were inconclusive.

No significant reduction in phytic acid was observed. Furthermore, statistical assessment of vicine and convicine was not possible; however, a correlating increase was observed in concentrations of phytic acid, vicine, and convicine during the stationary growth phase in *S. cerevisiae* fermentations.

Resumé

Faba bønner er i stigende grad anerkendt som en bæredygtig kilde til plantebaseret protein. Dog er deres ernæringsmæssige værdi og fordøjelighed begrænset af tilstedeværelsen af antinutritionelle faktorer (ANFs), herunder fytinsyre, oligosakkarider fra raffinose-familien (RFOs), vicin og convicin.

Formålet med dette speciale var at undersøge, om indholdet af ANFs i faba bønner kan reduceres gennem fermentering af et simuleret faba bønne-substrat bestående af 7 % faba bønne proteinkoncentrat, 1 % glukose og 1 % sukrose. Fermenteringen blev udført med monokulturer af *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (*S. cerevisiae*), *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* (*L. plantarum*) og *Bacillus subtilis* natto (*B. subtilis* natto). Mikrobiel vækst blev overvåget efter 0, 6, 24 og 48 timer i fermenteringer ved 30°C i blue-cap flasker for at vurdere, om hvorvidt mikroorganismene kan vokse i faba bønne-matricer. De maksimale cellekoncentrationer blev målt til $(1.64 \pm 0.08) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL for *S. cerevisiae*, $(7.75 \pm 0.25) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL for *L. plantarum* og $(2.00 \pm 0.25) \times 10^6$ CFU/mL for *B. subtilis* natto efter 48 timer. Dog udviste *B. subtilis* natto en 10-foldreduktion i cellekoncentration inden for de første 6 timer af fermenteringen.

Derudover blev potentialet for forlængelse af substratets holdbarhed vurderet ved at analysere produktionen af antimikrobielle molekyler, specifikt organiske syrer. Dette blev undersøgt ved at overvåge pH-niveauer og analysere organisk syreproduktion via HPLC gennem hele fermenteringsperioden. pH-værdien faldt signifikant til 4.05 ± 0.00 for *L. plantarum* og 5.30 ± 0.01 for *S. cerevisiae* i den stationære vækstfase, mens *B. subtilis* natto ikke udviste en signifikant reduktion i pH og endte med en slut-pH på 5.56 ± 0.02 .

Koncentrationerne af eddikesyre, mælkesyre og citronsyre blev målt over hele fermenteringsforløbet. Både *B. subtilis* natto og *S. cerevisiae* producerede eddikesyre. *S. cerevisiae* producerede en koncentration på 1.78 ± 0.26 g/kg efter 24 timer, men metaboliserede efterfølgende eddikesyren sammen med citronsyren. *B. subtilis* natto producerede 1.17 ± 0.04 g/kg eddikesyre efter 48 timer. *L. plantarum* producerede derimod signifikante mængder mælkesyre i den stationære vækstfase og nåede en koncentration på 5.04 ± 0.01 g/kg.

Både *L. plantarum* og *S. cerevisiae* var i stand til at metabolisere raffinose fermentativt, men *S. cerevisiae* var ikke i stand til at assimilere den. Resultaterne for *B. subtilis* nato vedrørende raffinose fermentering var inkonklusiv.

Der blev ikke observeret en signifikant reduktion i fytinsyre. Derudover var det ikke muligt at lave en statistisk vurdering af vicin og convicin koncentrationer, dog blev en korrelerede stigning i fytinsyre, vicin og convicin observeret i den stationære væksthase i *S. cerevisiae*-fermenteringerne.

List of abbreviations

2HCT: 2-hydroxycarboxylate transporters

AA: Amino acid

AN: Anti nutrient

ANF: antinutritional factor

B. subtilis: *Bacillus subtilis*

EMP: Emden-Meyerhof Parnas

FAA: Free amino acid

FBPC: Faba bean protein concentrate

FBPC-substrate: Faba bean substrate

FFA: Free fatty acids

GIT: Gastrointestinal tract

HPLC: High-Performance Liquid Chromatography

L. plantarum: *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*

LCA: Life cycle analysis

LCA: Life cycle analysis

RFOs: Raffinose family oligosaccharides

S. cerevisiae: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

TAG: Triacylglycerol

TCA: Tricarboxylic acid

Background

Introduction

The world population is thought to surpass 10 billion by 2050. With that comes an increased need for protein sources. Plants protein may be a source which should be explored further to mitigate this additional need. Furthermore, consumers are becoming more aware of plants as a healthy source of protein. Thus, plant protein is becoming more popular among consumers across all age groups. Proteins are essential to sustain life, and the human body demands essential amino acids from exogenous sources. However, plant derived proteins can be low in some essential amino acids and the proteins are less digestible than animal protein (Aimutis 2022).

Various life cycle assessment (LCA) studies have shown that vegan and vegetarian products score lower in impact categories compared to meat products overall, showing the environmental benefit of plant-based food sources (Takacs *et al.* 2022; Tang *et al.* 2024). However, McAuliffe *et al.* (2022) discusses issues, with comparing meat products with their plant-based analogues directly due to various nutritional aspects. These aspects, such as antinutritional factors (ANFs) bioavailability and digestibility are often not accounted for.

A LCA of faba bean cultivation in Canada, showed that the cultivation of faba beans scores lower in most impact categories than other legume crops. This is due to the low input requirement of the crop, which could indicate that faba bean cultivation in colder climates is more sustainable compared to other legumes (Bamber *et al.* 2024).

Faba beans are rich in plant proteins, but their nutritional value is limited due to their content of various anti-nutritional factors (ANFs), such as phytic acid, raffinose-family oligosaccharides (RFOs), vicine, and convicine, among others (Dhull *et al.* 2022). Several processing methods are used to reduce or eliminate ANFs, with fermentation being considered a sustainable approach (Senanayake *et al.* 2023).

Aim and objective

Aim

This project aims to investigate the growth potential of various microorganisms in faba beans and their ability to reduce anti-nutritional factors, as well as discuss the potential effects of fermentation on shelf life.

Objectives

- Investigate the growth potential of selected microorganisms in faba beans
 - By conducting single-species fermentation of a simulated faba bean substrate using:
 - *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*
 - *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*
 - *Bacillus subtilis*
- Assess the potential of microbial fermentation to reduce anti-nutritional factors
 - By evaluating the microorganisms' ability to degrade raffinose family oligosaccharides by investigating raffinose utilization
- By determining changes in anti-nutritional compound concentrations over time of:
 - Phytic acid
 - Vicine and convicine
- Discuss the potential effect of fermentation on shelf life
 - By monitoring pH and organic acid production over time, including:
 - Acetic acid
 - Citric acid
 - Lactic acid

Theoretical framework

Overview of faba beans

Vicia faba L., commonly referred to as faba bean, fava bean, horse bean and broad bean, is a legume crop cultivated worldwide. This includes Denmark, as the crop tolerates colder climates as well as thrives in most soil types. The crop is the 5th most produced pulse globally and the annual production is estimated at over 4.5 billion tonnes on average (Bangar & Dhull 2022).

Common species and phenotypes

The legume belongs to the family Fabaceae with 16,000-19,000 species in 750 genera (Punia *et al.* 2019). The main species consist of *Vicia faba L. major* (large-sized broad beans), *Vicia faba L. equine* (medium-sized faba beans) as well as *Vicia faba L. minor* (small-sized horse bean/ tick bean). Among the varieties the *Vicia faba L. major* and *Vicia faba L. minor* are the most studied. Between the two, variations in phenotypic expression can be observed in relation to shape and size. Shapes can be either cylindrical, spherical, flat-oval or pyramidal (Bangar & Dhull 2022). In Figure 1 a picture of fresh faba bean and pods can be seen.

Figure 1. Picture of fresh faba bean pod and seeds obtained from Pexels.com

Bean physiology

The faba bean is a dicot embryo composed of two cotyledons enclosed by a tough seed coat. The cotyledon contains micro -and macro nutrients essential for development of the plant. Macro nutrients are organised as starch granules as well as oil and protein bodies in storage cells called parenchyma cells as seen in Figure 2 (Pallares Pallares *et al.* 2021).

Figure 2. General structure of a faba bean seed and its cotyledon components. The diagram illustrates the overall structure of a faba bean seed, showing the seed coat, epicotyl, cotyledon, and embryo. The cotyledon is magnified to show its main storage components, including protein bodies, oil bodies, and starch granules. Created in BioRender.

In plants cells starches are organised as hierarchical structures in four levels (Figure 3). The first level has the simplest starch structure and is composed of individual glucose chains linked by glycosidic bonds as either straight chains linked by α -1,4 bonds or as branches linked by α -1,6 bonds. Furthermore, the starches are organised as anhydroglucose polymers that form whole starch molecules, specifically amylose and amylopectin, the latter having the most branched structure. Amylose and amylopectin forms lamella with alternating layers of crystalline regions of tightly packed short chains of amylopectin as well as amorphous regions of loosely packed amylose and amylopectin (Figure 3). These alternating layers form concentric growth rings that make up individual starch granules ranging in size from 1-100 μm (Do *et al.* 2018).

Figure 3. Hierarchical organization of a plant starch granule, showing its concentric rings composed of alternating amorphous and crystalline lamellae, lamellar arrangement and branched structure of amylopectin and linear structure of amylose.

The proteins are stored in spherical specialized subcellular organelles consisting of an inner amorphous protein matrix enveloped by a membrane called protein bodies. They range in sizes from 0.1-25 μm and tend to associate with the larger starch granules, thereby influencing starch functionality and digestibility. While the distribution of various proteins within protein bodies are detailed for, for instance, sorghum (Do *et al.* 2018) these details remain unelucidated about faba bean storage protein.

Similar to proteins, fat is stored in larger spherical organelles ranging in diameters from 0.5-2.5 μm . These are composed of a triacylglycerol (TAG) core encapsulated and stabilized by a phospholipid monolayer embedded with structural surface proteins (Figure 4), namely oleosin, caleosin and stereoleosin, which contribute to membrane integrity. (Do *et al.* 2018).

Figure 4. Model structure of an oil body with a triacylglycerol (TAG) core, surrounded by a phospholipid monolayer and surface proteins.

Nutritional composition

Faba beans are used as a food and feed source and are mostly consumed dry. They have a relatively high protein content as well as being a source for lipids and complex carbohydrates (Bangar & Dhull 2022). They have a high content of lysine- and sulphur-containing proteins, as well as secondary metabolites and bioactive compounds (Mayer Labba *et al.* 2021). The nutritional composition of faba beans is highly dependent genotypic traits associated with cultivar type as well as external and environmental factors (Martineau-Côté *et al.* 2022).

Carbohydrates

Faba beans are rich in carbohydrates (51-68%). This fraction of faba bean mainly consists of sugars, starch and dietary fibre. Sugars in this fraction consist mainly of oligosaccharides belonging to the raffinose family (RFOs), such as raffinose, verbascose and stachyose, which can cause gassiness/flatulence in humans. Out of the total carbohydrate fraction the main component is starch (41-58%). This fraction consists mainly of amylose and amylopectin arranged in granules which can vary in shape and regularity. The granules are tightly bound and, as such, have poor solubility and swelling attributes. A large portion of starch consists of resistant starch (46.7%) and slowly digestible starch (34.5%), while only a small portion of readily digestible starch (15.3%). Faba beans are also rich in dietary fibre, though the highest concentration is found in the seed coat (82.3%) while the whole bean consists of 15-30%. This fraction is composed of mainly cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin (Dhull et al. 2022).

Proteins

The protein content in faba bean makes up about 27.5% of faba bean flour. The protein fraction mainly consists of globulins (roughly 70 %-80 %) (Vogelsang-O'Dwyer et al. 2020; Stone et al. 2024). These are salt soluble and globular proteins rich in glutamic acid, aspartic acid, arginine and leucine (Warsame et al. 2018). Aside from the high globulin content faba beans also contain smaller fractions of albumins (23%), prolamins (2%) and glutamins (<1%) (Stone et al. 2024).

Globulins

Various globulins are found as storage proteins in the protein bodies of faba beans. Legumin constitutes around 50% of the globulin fraction on average (Warsame et al. 2018; Warsame et al. 2020) while vicilin and convicilin combined constitute around 27% of the storage protein in faba beans. However, it should be noted that large variation can be seen among genotypes (Warsame et al. 2020).

Legumin consists of two subunits, one (legumin A) which contain methionine residues and one (legumin B) which does not. The subunits are further comprised of α - and β -chains held together by disulphide bridges. While the subunits of legumin (~60 kDa), vicilin (50 kDa) and convicilin (~70 kDa) are of comparable size, legumin can organize into both trimers and hexamers, while vicilin and convicilin organize only into trimers (Warsame et al. 2018; Sharan et al. 2021) as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Structural organization of faba bean storage proteins. The diagram illustrates the assembly of legumin, vicilin, and convicilin proteins in faba beans. Legumin consists of α - and β -chains linked by disulphide bridges, forming subunits (60 kDa), trimers (180 kDa), and hexamers (360 kDa). Vicilin and convicilin assemble into trimers (150 kDa and 210 kDa, respectively) from their monomeric subunits.

Protein digestibility

Plant proteins tend to have a large tight globular structure, which can make cleavage sites inaccessible to enzymes compared to animal derived proteins. Additionally, some temperature and pH conditions during food preparation can influence accessibility. This is for instance seen when preparing isolates, where aggregates larger than casein micelles are seen. These factors negatively impact the digestibility of the proteins by enzymes despite the high protein concentration of isolates (Gouseti *et al.* 2023).

Lipids

The lipid fraction of faba beans is relatively low compared to other legumes, typically accounting for ~1–3% of the total dry weight (Martineau-Côté *et al.* 2022; Moussou *et al.* 2017). The lipid content is primarily composed of TAGs, phospholipids, and glycolipids, with phospholipids being the predominant class due to their role in cell membrane structure and oil body stabilization (Do *et al.* 2018). The phospholipid fraction consists mainly of phosphatidylcholine and phosphatidylethanolamine (Yoshida *et al.* 2009), which play key roles in emulsification and interaction with proteins in food systems.

The fatty acid profile of faba beans consists mainly of unsaturated fatty acids, with linoleic acid (C18:2) and oleic acid (C18:1) being the most abundant. These are followed by smaller amounts of saturated fatty acids, such as palmitic acid (C16:0) (Badjona *et al.* 2023). Due to the high amount of polyunsaturated fatty acids, the lipid fraction of faba beans is prone to oxidation, which can influence shelf-life and stability in food applications.

Bioactive compounds and antinutritional factors

Faba beans contain a variety of bioactive compounds such as L-DOPA which is a precursor to dopamine as well as total phenolics and flavonoids which have antioxidative properties among other reported benefits. However, these antioxidants are by far most located in the seed coat and L-DOPA is sensitive to processing and can be completely removed by dehulling and boiling. Additionally, faba beans contain various antinutritional factors (ANFs), such as phytic acid, pyrimidine glycosides, RFOs, lectins, saponins tannins and trypsin inhibitors, which all have negative effects on digestion and/or nutritional value. Of these, the ones researched in this thesis will be further described in the following section (Dhull *et al.* 2022).

Raffinose family oligosaccharides

The RFOs raffinose, stachyose and verbascose are found in faba beans where verbascose presents the highest fraction (Elango *et al.* 2022). Lattanzio *et al.* (1986) found that between 15 faba bean cultivars the raffinose content range to be 0.12-0.29% of the whole dry seed while stachyose presented 0.46-1.02% and verbascose 0.82-1.61%.

They hold various important roles in the plant health in terms of physiological and cellular function as well as being relatively simple sugars accessible to the plant during the germination process.

While they have some positive effects such as prebiotic, antidiabetic, antiallergenic among others, they are considered ANFs. This is due to their indigestibility in the human gut causing discomfort in the form of flatulence, cramps and nausea. (Elango *et al.* 2022).

RFOs consists of various (1 →6)-linked galactose chains which is linked to a sucrose moiety via an $\alpha(1 \rightarrow 6)$ linkage. Raffinose has one galactose unit while stachyose has two and verbascose has three (Sanyal *et al.* 2023). In Figure 6 below the structures of raffinose, stachyose and verbascose are displayed.

Figure 6. Chemical structures of RFOs; raffinose, stachyose, and verbascose. These carbohydrates consist of a sucrose core (consisting of α -D-glucose and β -D-fructose) with one or more α -D-galactose units linked via α -(1→6) glycosidic bonds. Raffinose contains a single galactose unit, stachyose has two, and verbascose has three, demonstrating their stepwise structural expansion. Adapted from Zhang *et al.* 2019

The indigestibility of RFOs can be attributed to the lack of α -galactosidases in the upper part of the human digestive system. As a result, these oligosaccharides make it to the large intestine where colonic bacteria present can ferment them. This releases various gasses ultimately causing flatulence and additional discomfort. However, the presence of RFOs in legumes can be mitigated by various processing methods (Elango *et al.* 2022).

Vogelsang-O'Dwyer *et al.* (2020) found that wet fractionation for the manufacture of protein isolates reduced RFO content significantly. However, the contents of RFOs in dry fractionated protein concentrate increased compared to dehulled faba bean flour.

Another study found that soaking followed by cooking could reduce the total oligosaccharide content by 41-43% in faba beans (Stone *et al.* 2021). Al-Kaisey *et al.* (2003) showed that γ -

radiation could fully eliminate RFOs, provided that a high enough dose of radiation was given.

Additionally, germination has been shown to decrease the RFO content, with a total elimination of raffinose after 24 hrs of germination and significant reductions of stachyose at 24 hrs and verbascose after 48 hrs of germination (Wei *et al.* 2022).

Phytic acid

Phytic acid is considered an ANF found in cotyledon of legumes such as faba beans. They function as storage molecules for phosphorous, minerals and nutrients in pulses. They have an important role in supplying nutrients to the plants, especially during seed germination (Zehring *et al.* 2022). Phytic acid accumulates during seed maturation as mono- and divalent cationic salts, referred to as phytates. Phytic acid is a cyclic structure composed of a myo-inositol ring attached to six negatively charged phosphate groups (Figure 7), thus resulting in a strong negative net charge. The charge allows the molecule to chelate positively charged molecules such as proteins as well as divalent and trivalent mineral ions, including $\text{Fe}^{2+/3+}$, Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , thereby reducing their bioavailability. These ANFs bind protein and form complexes, resulting in lower protein solubility as well as inhibition of enzymatic activity of e.g. digestive enzymes, thereby decreasing the nutritional value of plants, such as faba beans (Gemedé & Ratta 2014).

Phytates are degraded by phytase, an enzyme found mainly in plants and microorganisms. Phytase is a heat-labile hydrolytic enzyme, which dephosphorylates phytic acid into myo-inositol and free orthophosphate by hydrolysis (Figure 7). Dephosphorylation occurs in a series of steps, whereby

partly phosphorylated intermediate molecules with different chelating capabilities are generated (Luo *et al.* 2009).

Figure 7. Enzymatic hydrolysis of phytic acid by phytase. The reaction illustrates the breakdown of phytic acid into inositol and phosphate ions (PO₄²⁻) through the action of phytase.

Phytates are highly resistant to thermal processing, as they are heat-stable while their enzymatic counterpart is heat-labile, thus processing such as cooking only decreases their concentration marginally. However, prolonged soaking, seed germination and fermentation can aid in promoting the activity of phytase (Bangar & Dhull 2022). Sharma & Sehgal (1992) found that soaking of faba beans lead to a decrease in the phytate concentration in up to 4% after 12 hrs of soaking in 37°C water. Additionally, they found that cooking of the soaked whole beans as well as soaked and dehulled beans led to a reduction in 32% and 35%, respectively.

However, some evidence in literature suggests that phytic acid may also interact with proteins during heat treatment. These interactions can be binary (protein-phytate-protein) or ternary (linkages catalysed by divalent cations) (Wang & Guo 2021). Wang *et al.* (2018) found that protein unfolding during denaturation created conditions in which phytate could bind to some subunits in soy proteins. After this complex formation aggregation of denatured protein could occur and it was found that approximately a third of the phytate could form complexes with proteins. Another study investigating pH effects on ternary and binary complex formation suggested that formation of aggregates may shelter phytate from enzymatic degradation (Selle *et al.* 2012). The general principle of the shielding of phytate by denaturation and aggregation can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. General principle of protein-phytate complex formation caused by heat treatment followed by aggregation. Adapted from Wang *et al.* 2018

Vicine and convicine

The pyrimidine glycosides vicine and convicine (Figure 9) make up to ~1% of the total weight of faba beans (Khamassi *et al.* 2013). These bioactive, water-soluble compounds are stored in the cotyledon and are highly heat-stable, making them resistant to processing. They can be reduced by wet protein purification (Vogelsang-O'Dwyer *et al.* 2020), though this method is expensive and unsustainable. They can also be removed through hydrolysis, breaking them down into their unstable aglycones (Pulkkinen *et al.* 2019).

Figure 9. Chemical structures of vicine and convicine drawn with ChemDraw (version X) software. Adapted from Bangar & Dhull 2022.

The solubility of vicine and convicine is pH-dependent; vicine has a maximum solubility at acidic pH, whereas convicine has a maximum at alkaline pH. The compounds exhibit keto-enol and amine-imine tautomerism. The enol form, which is pH dependent and formed under acidic and alkaline conditions, is less stable than the keto form (Rizzello *et al.* 2016; Bangar & Dhull 2022).

Vicine and convicine has potential toxic effects, as some individuals are sensitive to the compounds. Vicine and convicine are hydrolysed in the liver or GIT into their corresponding aglycones, divicine and isouramil. These have strong oxidative potential and oxidises red blood cells in people with glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency, leading to haemolytic anaemia, also known as favism (Khazaei *et al.* 2019).

Additionally, various studies show that reduction of vicine and convicine to their respective aglycones is facilitated by enzymatic hydrolysis with β -glucosidases from various sources such as almonds (Pulkkinen *et al.* 2016), apricot (Ali & Shakir 2023) as well as *Aspergillus* spp. (McKay 1992).

Processing of faba beans

Protein extraction

Due to the high protein content and favourable amino acid profile, faba beans are increasingly used as a plant-protein source. Various methods are used for extracting faba bean proteins, these are broadly categorized as wet- and dry fractionation processing methods as seen in Figure 10 (Agrawal *et al.* 2024; Stone *et al.* 2024). However, in this study, the protein concentrate (Vestkorn) used was provided pre-processed using dry fractionation. Therefore, though multiple extraction methods exist, the focus here is on highlighting the properties of protein concentrates derived specifically from dry fractionation.

Figure 10. General overview of faba bean flour and protein processing. Flowchart is made with Lucidchart and adapted from Stone *et al.* 2024.

Dry fractionation

Dry fractionation is a mechanical separation process in which faba bean seeds are milled into a fine flour, followed by **air classification** to separate protein-rich and starch-rich fractions based on particle size and density (Rivera *et al.* 2024). Despite this separation, other molecules such as small amounts of fat as well as antinutrients remain in the protein enriched flours (Vogelsang-O’Dwyer *et al.* 2020). Some protein remains attached to the surface of starch granules. The starch content can be gradually reduced by multiple rounds of milling and air classification (Gueguen 1983).

Vogelsang-O’Dwyer *et al.* 2020 found that protein-rich faba bean flour produced via dry

fractionation, had a protein content of 64.1 g/100 g, a fat content of 2.43 g/100 g and a total carbohydrate content of 28.7 g/100 g dry matter, with a starch content of 7.55 ± 0.235 g/100 g dry matter. Additionally, dry fractionation is an energy-efficient and solvent-free technique, making it a more sustainable method for extracting protein, compared to wet fractionation.

Alternative extraction methods

Other methods, such as alkaline solubilization and isoelectric precipitation, are commonly used to obtain high-purity protein isolates from legumes (Stone *et al.* 2024). These techniques often yield higher protein purity but require significant water and energy inputs and may alter protein functionality (Vogelsang-O'Dwyer *et al.* 2020). While wet extraction is not the focus of this study, its differences from dry fractionation are relevant when considering the composition of the protein concentrate if used in e.g. fermentations.

Selected microorganisms often used in plant-based fermentations

Saccharomyces cerevisiae

Taxonomy, ecology and industrial relevance

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (*S. cerevisiae*) is a yeast species belonging to the phylum Ascomycota. It is widely known for its role in brewing, baking, and winemaking, where it is valued for its ability to produce ethanol, CO₂, and flavor compounds (Bai *et al.* 2022). In the food industry, domesticated strains of *S. cerevisiae* are used for their fermentation capabilities depending on the application. These industrial strains are better characterized and controlled than wild-types, ensuring consistency in bread-making, beer brewing, and wine fermentation (Lahue *et al.* 2020).

S. cerevisiae is considered a generalist yeast due to its ability to thrive in diverse environments. It is commonly associated with glucose-rich environments, such in food productions, as well as in soil, fruit surfaces, trees, and insect-associated environments. This suggests that *S. cerevisiae* is a nomadic yeast, capable of surviving in various environments and transported by insects (Bai *et al.* 2022).

Morphology and growth characteristics

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (*S. cerevisiae*) is a unicellular eukaryote that varies in cell size and shape. Cells are typically ovoid or spherical, with sizes 7.5 µm × 5.5 µm on average and may form pseudohyphae (Chavez *et al.* 2024). Colonies appear smooth, round, moist and cream colored (Das & Dam 2024). The colonies are mostly flat but can be raised or folded (Reis *et al.* 2013). *S. cerevisiae* is a teleomorph yeast meaning that it can reproduce sexually through mating and asexually through budding where cell division occurs through mitosis. In *S. cerevisiae* budding occurs multilaterally (on all sides of the cell) (Chavez *et al.* 2024). Some *S. cerevisiae* strains exhibit flocculation, which is a phenotypic trait where multiple cells aggregate into clumps (flocs) and sediment out of suspension. *S. cerevisiae* strains such as NCYC 625 tend to flocculate (Schorr-Galindo *et al.* 2000), while other strains remain dispersed. Flocculation is influenced by temperature, pH, nutrient availability, and ethanol levels (Reis *et al.* 2013; Stratford 1989). In brewing and winemaking, flocculation aids in yeast cell removal, whereas excessive flocculation is undesirable in bio-ethanol production because can limit ethanol production (Reis *et al.* 2013).

The species can grow both aerobically and anaerobically (Feldmann 2012) with optimal temperatures ranging from 28-33°C though the species can grow from 10 to 40°C (Lip *et al.* 2020). *S. cerevisiae* is an acidophilic yeast, growing best at pH 4–6, though its optimal pH varies with temperature and oxygen availability (Narendranath & Power 2005). A study by Salari & Salari (2017) reported that at 30°C, the most optimal growth conditions were observed at pH 4 and a dissolved oxygen level of 5%, though the study did not test multiple temperature conditions.

Metabolism and technological properties

Carbohydrate metabolism

S. cerevisiae primarily utilizes glucose as an energy source. Under aerobic conditions, glucose enters the glycolytic pathway, producing pyruvate, NADH, and ATP. Pyruvate undergoes oxidative decarboxylation to form acetyl-CoA, which enters the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle, generating electron carriers used for ATP synthesis (Feldmann 2012).

Under anaerobic conditions, the TCA cycle is inactive, and glycolysis is upregulated to meet energy requirements of the cell. This leads to the Pasteur effect, where glucose uptake is increased, particularly at low glucose concentrations. Pyruvate is converted into acetaldehyde and then ethanol, regenerating NAD^+ which ensures glycolysis and ATP production does not cease (Feldmann 2012). A general overview of the pathways involved in the central carbohydrate metabolism of *S. cerevisiae* can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Overview depicting the central carbohydrate metabolism of *S. cerevisiae*, including glycolysis (black) anaerobic fermentation (red) and aerobic respiration (blue).

S. cerevisiae is known to produce acetic acid which contributes to acidity in alcoholic fermentations which is typically undesired (Cordente *et al.* 2013).

S. cerevisiae exhibits the Crabtree effect, which allows it to perform alcoholic fermentation even in the presence of oxygen at higher glucose levels. This is a type of catabolite repression, where aerobic respiration is downregulated in favor of fermentation. Additionally, glucose repression ensures glucose is preferentially utilized over other carbon sources. Once glucose is depleted, *S. cerevisiae* can switch to two-carbon substrates such ethanol and acetate for energy production. This occurs through the glyoxylate cycle, provided sufficient oxygen is available and is referred to as diauxie or diauxic growth (Feldmann 2012; Palma *et al.* 2018).

S. cerevisiae can metabolize other sugar and carbon sources if glucose is unavailable. *S. cerevisiae* can use galactose as the sole carbon source, but genes responsible for its uptake are repressed in the presence of glucose. *S. cerevisiae* also metabolizes disaccharides such as maltose, sucrose, and melibiose through enzymatic hydrolysis. Maltose is actively transported into the cell and cleaved by maltase, while invertase hydrolyzes sucrose into glucose and fructose. Additionally, *S. cerevisiae* produces intracellular hydrolases capable of degrading disaccharides, such as lactose and melibiose, into their constituent monosaccharides, further demonstrating the species' metabolic versatility. However, the ability to hydrolyze certain sugars, including melibiose, is strain-dependent (Feldmann 2012)

Protein metabolism

S. cerevisiae can utilize a wide range of nitrogen sources, though it exhibits a preference for specific amino acids including glutamate, aspartate, and arginine, which are found in faba beans, as well as other amino acid. The nitrogen from these preferred amino acids is used to synthesize glutamate, which acts as a precursor for approximately 85% of the cell's nitrogen. Meanwhile, the carbon from these amino acids is converted into pyruvate and α -ketoglutarate, which is why the presence or absence of preferred amino acids affects the growth rate and metabolism of *S. cerevisiae* (Ljungdahl & Daignan-Fornier 2012). Kasprowicz-Potocka et al. (2018) reported that fermentation of lupin seeds with *S. cerevisiae* led to a progressive increase in crude and true protein content over time, with some amino acid concentrations rising while others declined. *S. cerevisiae* has limited extracellular proteolytic activity, compared to lactic acid bacteria (LAB), but synergistic effects in co-cultures have been observed, enhancing proteolysis during fermentation (Christensen et al. 2022).

Lipid metabolism

Unlike other yeasts such as *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *S. cerevisiae* is not highly lipolytic and exhibits limited extracellular lipase activity (Kuncharoen *et al.* 2020). Though *S. cerevisiae* is not widely used for its role in lipid hydrolysis during fermentation, it expresses intracellular lipases and esterases which contribute to flavor development in fermented products. In wine and beer fermentations, lipid oxidation products and volatile fatty acids influence aroma profile (Styger *et al.* 2011). Although similar studies in legume-based fermentations are limited, these metabolic pathways may still influence the sensory properties in faba bean fermentations.

Role in ANF reduction

Phytic acid

S. cerevisiae has shown strain-dependent variability in its ability to degrade phytic acid. Romero-Espinoza *et al.* (2020) reported a reduction in phytic acid concentrations ranging from 61.9% to 67.7% in whole lupin flour after 24 hrs of fermentation with *S. cerevisiae*. They noted that fermentation enhances the activity of native plant phytases due to a moderate decrease in pH, which stimulates microbial metabolic activity. This, in turn, can lead to the production of microbial phytases; however, this depends on whether the microorganisms involved can produce phytase. Similarly, Kasprowicz-Potocka *et al.* (2017) observed a significant reduction in phytate content within the first 48 hrs of fermenting lupin meal with *S. cerevisiae*, which they attributed to fermentation-induced stimulation of the activity of native phytases. Additionally, Mikulski and Kłosowski (2018) analyzed 30 strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolated from various fermentation processes, such as baking and brewing, and observed significant variability in their ability to utilize phytic acid. Their findings revealed that only four out of the 30 strains were capable of significantly degrading phytic acid, with reductions ranging from approximately 5% to 45% across all strains. The reduction in phytate was attributed to extracellular phytases produced by the yeasts. These findings highlight the role of strain variation in the extent of phytic acid reduction.

RFOs

Romero-Espinoza *et al.* (2020) found that 24-hour fermentation of whole lupin flour with *S. cerevisiae* more than halved RFO concentrations. Kasprowicz-Potocka *et al.* (2018) further demonstrated that raffinose was fully degraded within 48 hrs, while complete hydrolysis of stachyose and verbascose was observed after 72 hrs of fermentation. Chen *et al.* (2024) also found strain variation in *S. cerevisiae*'s ability to utilize raffinose, which was demonstrated by differences in doubling time when raffinose was the sole carbon source. While the specific mechanism of RFO degradation was not discussed in these studies, Ostergaard *et al.* (2000) noted that invertase expressed in *S. cerevisiae*, hydrolyses raffinose into fructose and melibiose. Melibiose is further broken down by α -galactosidase into glucose and galactose, in melibiase-positive *S. cerevisiae* strains.

Furthermore, Hayford & Jespersen (1999) found that all 48 *S. cerevisiae* strains they investigated were able to assimilate raffinose, suggesting that raffinose utilization is a common trait within the species, although some strain-specific variation may still exist. This was corroborated by van der Aa Kühle *et al.* (2001) who observed strain variations in raffinose assimilation among *S. cerevisiae* strains isolated from Sorghum beer. **This shows that although many strains can assimilate raffinose, this trait is not present in all *S. cerevisiae* strains.**

Vicine and Convicine

The reduction of vicine and convicine has not been demonstrated to be facilitated by *S. cerevisiae* in fermentations. However, β -glucosidases, which facilitate the hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds, have been studied for their potential role in glycoside degradation. Hernández *et al.* (2003) observed **β -glucosidase activity in *S. cerevisiae* wine strains,** due to the enzyme's role in aroma compound formation, which could indicate a potential role in vicine and convicine hydrolysis. Additionally, Bonciani *et al.* (2018) researched β -glucosidase activity across various *S. cerevisiae* wine strains, finding strain variation. However, both studies investigated hydrolysis of glycosides such as arbutin and esculin, meaning **it is uncertain whether *S. cerevisiae* could directly hydrolyze vicine and/or convicine.**

Lactiplantibacillus plantarum

Taxonomy, ecology and industrial relevance

Lactiplantibacillus plantarum (*L. plantarum*), formerly known as *Lactobacillus plantarum*, belongs to the *Lactobacillus* genus, consisting of more than 260 highly diverse species (Zheng *et al.* 2020). It is considered a generalist among LAB due to its' ability to adapt to a wide range of environments, including the gastrointestinal tract of mammals, plants, and various human and animal-associated sources. *L. plantarum* is therefore commonly isolated from fresh plants and fermented foods, such as wine, beer, sourdough, olives, meats, and cheeses (Siezen & van Hylckama Vlieg 2011).

Morphology and growth characteristics

L. plantarum is a homofermentative, gram-positive, non-motile, and non-spore-forming bacterium. Cells appears as straight rods (~0.9-1.2 × 3.0-8.0 µm), occurring as single cells, in pairs, or in short chains. The species is microaerophilic and oxidase-negative (Nath *et al.* 2020). Under specific conditions, certain strains exhibit true catalase and manganese-containing pseudocatalase activities (Corsetti & Valmorri, 2011).

L. plantarum is mesophilic but can grow at temperatures down to 10–15°C, with optimal growth varying depending on strain and environmental conditions. Brinques *et al.* (2010) reported that *L. plantarum* strains isolated from Serrano cheese exhibited the highest biomass yield and lactic acid production at 30°C, in a complex medium. Similarly, Popova-Krumova *et al.* (2024) found that the optimal growth conditions for *L. plantarum* AC 11S were at pH 6.5 and 30°C, further confirming that optimum growth occurs at moderate temperatures. Colony morphology of *Lactobacilli* tends to be 2-5 mm, smooth, raised, glistening and white with entire margins (Than *et al.* 2022).

Metabolism and technological properties

Carbohydrate metabolism

L. plantarum metabolizes various carbon sources through the Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas (glycolytic) pathway, which converts hexoses primarily into D-lactic acid as well as L-lactic acid. In addition to utilizing carbohydrates, *L. plantarum* can metabolize citrate as a carbon source through specialized transport systems. The bacterium expresses 2-hydroxycarboxylate transporters (2HCT),

which is responsible for the uptake of extracellular citrate. Once inside the cell, citrate is converted into intermediates such as pyruvate, oxaloacetate, and acetate, contributing to energy production and metabolism (Yang *et al.* 2022) (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Overview the Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas glycolytic pathway found in *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis*, and the fate of pyruvate in *L. plantarum* under anaerobic conditions (red) and aerobic conditions (blue) and generally (black). Note that the TCA-cycle is incomplete in *L. plantarum*.

Under specific conditions, such as during the fermentation of certain substrates, *L. plantarum* can also produce acetic acid (Corsetti & Valmorri 2011). Sun *et al.* (2022) reported that *L. plantarum* degraded citric acid in fermented apricot juice, leading to the formation of acetic acid and other organic compounds. Additionally, when carbohydrate sources become limited, *L. plantarum* can further metabolize lactic acid into acetic acid. This was attributed to the activity of pyruvate oxidase, an enzyme whose activity is enhanced in the presence of oxygen and reduced in the presence of glucose. Furthermore, strain-dependent metabolic pathways contribute to the production of flavor compounds, such as acetoin, diacetyl, and 2,3-butanediol, from pyruvate (Corsetti & Valmorri 2011).

L. plantarum expresses β -glucosidase, an enzyme involved in the degradation of oligosaccharides and glycosylated polyphenols in faba beans. Resulting in enhanced nutrient bioavailability and reduction of anti-nutritional factors, while also contributing to aroma and flavor formation in fermentations (Paventi *et al.* 2024). Polyphenolic glycosides in faba beans, such as kaempferol- and quercetin-glucosides, are poorly absorbed compared to their aglycone forms due to higher molecular weight and hydrophilicity (Spanou *et al.* 2012). Research has shown that β -glucosidase activity in *L. plantarum* can alter the glycoside/aglycone ratio in fermented soy milk, thereby enhancing polyphenol bioavailability (Paventi *et al.* 2024).

Additionally, *L. plantarum* expresses α -galactosidase, an enzyme that hydrolyzes galactosides in RFOs. Studies on soy-based fermentations have demonstrated that *L. plantarum* can significantly degrade galactosides, thereby increasing the nutritional value of otherwise indigestible carbohydrates (Paventi *et al.* 2024).

Protein metabolism

L. plantarum exhibits proteolytic activity primarily due to oligoendopeptidases and aminopeptidases, which contribute to the formation of aroma and flavor compounds. These enzymes break down proteins into small peptides and free amino acids (FAAs), which can be further converted into hydroxy acids, aldehydes, alcohols, and carboxylic acids. This is caused by catabolism of aromatic and branched-chain amino acids through transamination (Paventi *et al.* 2024; Corsetti & Valmorri, 2011). Engels *et al.* (2022) reported that *L. plantarum*'s proteolytic activity led to a reduction of aldehydes and furans, that causes off-flavors in plant protein sources, including faba beans.

Lipid metabolism

Although *L. plantarum* is not highly lipolytic compared to some other microorganisms such as some *Bacillus* species (Parkouda *et al.* 2009), it expresses lipases and esterases that can hydrolyze lipids into free fatty acids (FFAs) and volatile compounds. These reactions are well-documented in dairy and fruit fermentations, where lipid oxidation products contribute to complex aroma profiles, as well as aiding in reduction of plant-off flavours (Paventi *et al.* 2024; Lorn 2021). While similar studies on legume fermentation are limited, these metabolic pathways may still play a role in sensory characteristics of faba bean-based products.

Role in ANF reduction

Phytic acid

Research indicates that *L. plantarum* exhibits low phytase activity, primarily due to the action of non-specific acid phosphatases rather than specific phytase enzymes. A study by Zamudio *et al.* (2001) found that although *L. plantarum* showed the highest phytase activity among the LAB species tested, the activity was minimal and attributed to a non-specific acid phosphatase with optimal activity at pH 5.5 and 65°C. Additionally, Rosa-Sibakov *et al.* (2018) found that faba bean flour fermented for 24 h by *L. plantarum* only led to a minor decrease (~9%) in phytic acid concentration. Similarly, Sandez Penidez *et al.* (2024) reported that quinoa snacks fermented with a high-phytase *L. plantarum* strain (CRL 1964) increased mineral bioavailability and micronutrient absorption by 1.1- to 2.7-fold in mice. Furthermore, Reale *et al.* (2007) demonstrated that LAB species, including *L. plantarum*, did not display significant extracellular phytase activity in cereal dough fermentations. Instead, phytate reduction was linked to acidification of the substrate during fermentation, which created optimal pH conditions for native plant phytases. This suggests that *L. plantarum* primarily reduces phytic acid by lowering pH to activate native phytases rather than through its own enzymatic activity.

RFOs

Azeke *et al.* (2005) reported that *L. plantarum* was capable of fermenting RFOs in African yam beans. After 24 hrs of fermentation, they observed an 88.1% reduction in total RFO content, with only 11.51% remaining. After 48 hrs, the total RFO content was further reduced to 92.5%. The authors attributed this degradation to α -galactosidase activity. Similarly, Kitum *et al.* (2020) fermented whole red haricot beans with *L. plantarum* and observed a 30.01% and 30.09% reduction in raffinose and stachyose concentrations, respectively, after 24 hrs. These reductions further increased to 54.54% and 53.07% after 48 hrs of fermentation." Verni *et al.* (2019) further demonstrated that *L. plantarum* could completely degrade verbascose in faba bean doughs fermented for 48 hrs. The lowest reduction observed was 87%, they additionally found that stachyose levels were also significantly reduced. Raffinose was fully degraded in most samples, apart from a few, where partial hydrolysis was observed.

Vicine and convicine

Verni *et al.* (2019) reported that the *L. plantarum* strain used in their study, known for high β -glucosidase activity, reduced convicine content by up to 75%. Similarly, Rizzello *et al.* (2016) demonstrated that fermenting faba bean flour with *L. plantarum* for 48 hrs led to a 90% reduction in vicine and 95% reduction in convicine, attributing this effect to β -glucosidase activity. Likewise, Kahala *et al.* (2023) found that *L. plantarum* strains could reduce vicine and convicine levels by more than 99% in cooked faba beans after 48 hrs of fermentation

Bacillus subtilis

Taxonomy, ecology and industrial relevance

Bacillus subtilis (*B. subtilis*) is a fast-growing bacterial species belonging to the *Bacillus* genus (Errington & van der Aart 2020). It is commonly associated with soil ecosystems, where members of this genus are abundant. Like other *Bacillus* species, *B. subtilis* plays an important role in supplying nutrients and protection against microbial pathogens for plants, due to its diverse metabolic capabilities. It produces a wide range of antimicrobial compounds, including antifungal compounds such as heptapeptides involved in swarming motility and biofilm formation, as well as chitinases that degrade chitin, a key component of fungal cell walls (Saxena *et al.* 2020). Additionally, it produces bacteriocins such as subtilin, which exhibit antibacterial activity against closely related species (Saxena *et al.*, 2020).

Aside from its ecological role, *B. subtilis* has a broad range of industrial applications. It is used in the biosynthesis of proteases, amylases, and riboflavin, and is involved in legume fermentations, such as the production of fermented soybeans (*natto*) (Errington & van der Aart 2020).

Morphology and growth characteristics

Vegetative cells of *B. subtilis* are rod-shaped, can be motile and form endospores. Cells are normally $>1 \mu\text{m} \times 2\text{-}6 \mu\text{m}$ in size and often form chains when growth conditions are optimal (Errington & van der Aart 2020).

The macromorphology is quite variable in terms of strain. Thus, colonies can be both round and irregularly shaped with a diameter of 2-4 mm. The margins can vary from undulate to fimbriate and the colour is white to creamy or brown with a dull and possibly wrinkled surface. The colonies

can appear as moist or mucoid to rough and crusty. Some strains may produce various pigments on certain substrates (De Vos *et al.* 2009).

B. subtilis is primarily an aerobic microorganism, though it can grow anaerobically in complex media containing glucose and, to a lesser extent, nitrate. According to Errington & van der Aart (2020), *B. subtilis* has an optimal growth temperature of 30–35°C, while De Vos *et al.* (2009) report a broader growth range from 5–20°C to 45–55°C, with an optimal temperature around 28–30°C.

Although the exact pH range for optimal growth varies among strains, studies suggest that *B. subtilis* can grow within pH 5.5–8.5 (De Vos *et al.* 2009). Strain-dependent variations in pH optima were further demonstrated by Aderibigbe & Odunfa (1990), who investigated three strains of *B. subtilis* isolated from fermented African locust bean (*iru*). Their findings showed that optimal growth occurred between pH 7 and 9, varying between strains. Additionally, Chen *et al.* (2022) reported that *B. subtilis* natto exhibited a wide growth range (pH 5–9), with the highest viable cell count observed at pH 5.5.

Metabolism and technological properties

B. subtilis is commonly isolated from various indigenous fermented foods in Asia and Africa, where it is utilized for its ability to alter the food matrix. Its metabolic activity modifies organoleptic properties, increases nutrient bioavailability, synthesizes vitamins, and alters texture, thereby improving the edibility of the food for human consumption (Parkouda *et al.* 2009).

Carbohydrate metabolism

Bacillus subtilis generates energy through glycolysis via the Embden-Meyerhof-Parnas pathway (Wushensky *et al.* 2018). Under anaerobic conditions, *B. subtilis* can grow and produce fermentation byproducts such as lactate, acetate, and ethanol (see Figure 13). However, its growth rate is significantly lower in anaerobic conditions compared to under aerobic (Ramos *et al.* 2000).

B. subtilis is known to acquire energy through glycolysis via the EMP pathway (Wushensky *et al.* 2018). Similar to *L. plantarum*, in addition to utilizing carbohydrates, *B. subtilis* can metabolize citrate as a carbon source through transporters from the 2HCT family. Chelation of divalent cations such as Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ enhances the uptake of citric acid (Krom *et al.* 2000). Once inside

the cell, citrate is converted into intermediates that enter the TCA cycle, contributing to cellular energy production and biosynthesis.

Figure 13. Overview of the carbohydrate metabolism in *B. subtilis* and pathways to production of metabolic byproducts under aerobic (blue) and anaerobic (red) conditions.

Additionally, *B. subtilis* produces a variety of enzymes, including amylases, galactanases, galactosidases, glucosidases, and fructofuranosidases, which break down polysaccharides and oligosaccharides into simpler sugars (Owusu-Kwarteng *et al.* 2022 Aderibigbe & Odunfa 1990).

Protein metabolism

B. subtilis exhibits diverse proteolytic activity, by utilizing both membrane-bound proteases and secreted extracellular proteases, such as the serine protease subtilisin. Additionally, intracellular proteases can be released into the environment through cell lysis, where they act on the extracellular matrix (Harwood & Kikuchi 2022). The proteolytic activity of *B. subtilis* breaks down proteins into peptides and FAAs, thus supplying nutrients to the food matrix thereby improving its nutritional value and digestibility. Additionally, ammonia is released, which increases the pH of the

environment. Therefore, these fermentations are commonly referred to as “alkaline fermentations” and typically begin spontaneously after an intense heat treatment. Due to their heat-resistant spores, *Bacillus* species can survive these conditions, which is why these types of fermentations contain diverse *Bacillus* species and strains (Owusu-Kwarteng *et al.* 2022).

Lipid metabolism

Lipolytic activity by *Bacillus* species has been observed in alkaline fermentations, though the extent varies depending on the substrate and the degree to which different species participate in the fermentation. *B. subtilis* generally exhibits lower lipolytic activity compared to other species involved in these fermentations, such as *Bacillus pumilus*. The diversity of *Bacillus* species involved, influences the release of FFAs into the food matrix (Owusu-Kwarteng *et al.* 2022). However, *B. subtilis* is still capable of producing various lipolytic enzymes, including phospholipases, lipases, and esterases (Eggert *et al.* 2001).

Textural modification

During alkaline fermentation of seeds, the matrix softens, suggesting that *B. subtilis* may produce pectic enzymes that contribute to the breakdown of plant material. *B. subtilis* is known to influence texture through the production of cell wall-degrading enzymes, such as polygalacturonase-degrading enzymes, including pectin lyases, pectate lyase, and polygalacturonase (Ochiai *et al.* 2007). Additionally, some *Bacillus* species produce exopolysaccharides, which can further alter texture. In the Japanese fermented soybean product “natto”, the mucilage or slime consists of both protein and carbohydrate components, indicating that proteolysis may also play a role in texture modification, depending on the strain (Parkouda *et al.* 2009).

Role in ANF reduction

RFOs

B. subtilis has been shown to utilize intracellular α -galactosidase for the degradation of RFOs (Heravi *et al.* 2019). Zhang *et al.* (2021) further demonstrated that fermenting soybean meal with *B. subtilis* natto for aquafeed resulted in a >90% reduction in raffinose. Similarly, a study on various legume substrates, including faba bean, found that fermentation with different *Bacillus* species and strains isolated from soumbala led to a reduction in raffinose, along with other RFOs such as stachyose and verbascose. Moreover, *B. subtilis* was found to be more effective at degrading RFOs compared to *Bacillus pumilus* (Fernández-Varela *et al.* 2024).

Phytic acid

B. subtilis has been reported to produce phytases, involved in phytic acid degradation (Saxena *et al.* 2020). These findings were corroborated by Zhang *et al.* (2021), who observed a significant reduction in phytic acid caused by fermentation of soybean meal with *B. subtilis* natto. Similarly, Olagunju *et al.* (2018) studied spontaneous fermentation of tamarind seeds with various *Bacillus* species, including *B. subtilis*, and reported similar results. Their study found both a decrease in phytic acid content as well as an increase in rise in phosphorus content as well as in certain divalent cationic minerals, such as iron.

Vicine and convicine

Similar to *S. cerevisiae*, research on the ability of *B. subtilis* to degrade vicine and convicine is limited. However, β -glucosidase activity has been studied in various *B. subtilis* strains. It has been shown that enzymatic activity varies depending on the producing strain (Rai *et al.* 2017). Furthermore, Kuo *et al.* (2012) reported that maximum β -glucosidase activity in *B. subtilis* natto occurs between 10 and 15 hrs of fermentation. However, it is important to note that these studies did not test activity on vicine or convicine but rather p-nitrophenyl- β -D-glucoside. Therefore, it remains uncertain whether the β -glucosidases produced by *B. subtilis* would act vicine and convicine.

Co-culturing and synergism in anti-nutrient reduction Comment Siw

Co-culture and sequential fermentations using *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis* natto have been studied individually for their potential to degrade antinutrients and produce metabolites. However, studies exploring the combined influence of these microorganisms on ANFs in legumes are somewhat limited. Still, literature on co-fermentation of the species in plant matrices can be explored to some degree.

S. cerevisiae and *L. plantarum*

A study by Zhang *et al.* (2021) investigating single-species and co-culture fermentations of sourdough with *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* found that the pH in co-fermentations was comparable to that of single-species fermentation with *L. plantarum*. They also observed that co-culturing had a slight impact on the growth patterns of both microorganisms. During the early stages of fermentation (0–2 hrs), the growth rate of both species was slower in co-cultures compared to their growth in single-species fermentations. Additionally, the growth rate of *S. cerevisiae* was reduced in co-culture fermentations.

Another study by Yang *et al.* (2024) examining the interactions between *L. plantarum* and *S. cerevisiae* in relation to fermentation temperature of Baijiu, a Chinese alcoholic beverage made from sorghum. The results showed that at temperatures above 15°C, the growth and lactic acid production of *L. plantarum* were inhibited in co-culture with *S. cerevisiae*, whereas the growth and ethanol production of *S. cerevisiae* remained unaffected. Proteomic analysis revealed that enzymatic activity related to glycolysis and lactate dehydrogenase was downregulated in *L. plantarum* in co-culture, explaining the inhibition of lactic acid fermentation. It should be noted that in this case the substrate was enzymatically predigested with α -amylase and amyloglucosidase. In addition, (Terefe *et al.* 2022) found that co-culture fermentation resulted in a higher reduction of phytic acid (91.11%) compared to single-species fermentations with *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* in fermented cassava leaves. This suggests that synergistic effects may enhance phytic acid degradation. Similar results were reported by (Terefe *et al.* 2021), who observed a 66% reduction in phytic acid concentrations after 48 hrs of maize fermentation with *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum*.

S. cerevisiae and *B. subtilis*

The growth of *S. cerevisiae* and *B. subtilis* in two-species fermentation systems remains unelucidated. Nevertheless, since *B. subtilis* grows best at aerobic conditions (Ramos *et al.* 2000) and *S. cerevisiae* is capable of both aerobic respiration and anaerobic fermentation (Feldmann 2012), they could possibly grow together provided that the proteolytic activity of *B. subtilis* stimulates the growth by providing FAA sources for *S. cerevisiae* as it can for other microorganisms (Chen *et al.* 2021). Additionally, these two species could grow well together in environments where the pH and temperature remain suitable for both species. This could be somewhat of a challenge as *S. cerevisiae* prefers both lower pH (Salari & Salari 2017; De Vos *et al.* 2009) and temperature (Errington & van der Aart 2020; Lip *et al.* 2020; Narendranath & Power 2005) compared to *B. subtilis*. Additionally, because *S. cerevisiae* is a Crabtree positive yeast and may produce ethanol under aerobic conditions (Feldmann 2012) thus possibly inhibiting the growth of *B. subtilis*. Conversely, *B. subtilis* may produce antifungal compounds (Saxena *et al.* 2020) which could inhibit the growth of *S. cerevisiae* in a co-fermentation. If synergy can be obtained during growth between the two, perhaps this will translate to the degradation of antinutritional compounds as well.

B. subtilis and *L. plantarum*

A study by Chen *et al.* (2021) on co-fermentation of *B. subtilis* natto and *L. plantarum* on liquid state lentil substrate found that the growth of *L. plantarum* could be enhanced when inoculated with *B. subtilis* natto. The authors proposed that the synergistic effect might be due to the oxygen removal from the substrate by *B. subtilis* natto as well as the proteolytic activity strain. This could have provided *L. plantarum* with FAAs which may stimulate growth. They noted that elevating the initial cell count of *B. subtilis* might increase competition between the two species and instead inhibit growth of *L. plantarum*. Additionally, it was found that α -glucosidase activity decreased in co-fermentations. While studies on RFO reduction between the two species are lacking, a study by Fernández-Varela *et al.* 2024. on liquid state fermentation on legume proteins showed that fermentations with *B. subtilis* alone were more effective in degrading RFOs compared to fermentations where *Lactobacillus* species were included. It should be noted that *L. plantarum* was not included in that analysis in the paper.

Organic acids in food preservation

This section focuses on acetic acid and lactic acid, as they are fermentation byproducts of *S.*

cerevisiae, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis* natto, and can also serve as alternative carbon sources in fermentations. Citric acid is included due to its well-documented role in food preservation and its potential metabolic role in *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis* natto.

Organic acids have multiple benefits in foods and can act as flavor compounds, acidification agents and have been shown to have antimicrobial effects which varies between the acids (Punia Bangar et al. 2022). As such the antimicrobial hurdle effect of organic acids is an interplay between pH and pK_a (Bushell et al. 2019). The antimicrobial effects of organic acids are well established and known to be mostly influenced by their pK_a (Rossi et al. 2021).

The pK_a is the pH-value where an equilibrium is obtained and thus represents the threshold above which an acid exists mostly in its dissociated form and below in its undissociated form (Reijenga et al. 2013). Because organic acids are weak acids and have a higher pK_a-values they can exist mostly dissociated at higher pH compared to stronger acids. This enhances their antimicrobial effect (Punia Bangar et al. 2022).

The mechanism of the antimicrobial effect of organic acids is generally regarded the ability of undissociated acids to freely diffuse across cell membranes. Because the intracellular pH is higher than the extracellular pH, the acids dissociate, thus lowering pH and inhibiting DNA replication. To compensate for this proton pumps are activated, which forces the cell to spend energy on maintaining the intracellular pH (Rossi et al. 2021). The accumulation of protons and lowering of the intracellular pH may be intolerable to the cell, reducing the growth of the cell or even causing cell death (Trček et al. 2015).

fresh plant produce contains various human pathogenic organisms. They originate from pre-harvest sources such as soil, irrigation etc. or post-harvest due to human handling, processing etc. Some of these organisms include *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Listeria monocytogenes* (*L. monocytogenes*), *Bacillus cereus* (*B. cereus*), among many others (Beuchat et al. 1995).

Acetic acid

Acetic acid is known for its strong antimicrobial properties and has a pK_a of 4.75, the equilibrium is reached at a relatively high pH and is has a high proportion of its undissociated form (Punia Bangar et al. 2022). The ratio of acetic acid and acetate at the pK_a of acetic acid can be seen in Figure 14. Bangar *et al.* (2022) reported that acetic acid produced by LAB can inhibit various pathogenic species such as *B. cereus*, *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp., among others. Park *et al.* (2021) showed that the minimal inhibitory concentration of acetic acid was 0.125% for inhibition of psychrotolerant *B. cereus* strains isolated from lettuce.

Figure 14. Overview of approximate concentrations of dissociated and undissociated acetic acid at $pH=pK_a$.

Lactic acid

Compared to acetic acid, lactic acid has a lower antimicrobial effect. Lactic acid has a pK_a of 3.86, which means that the equilibrium threshold is lower. Therefore, more lactic acid will be dissociated at the same pH compared to acetic acid (Punia Bangar et al. 2022). The ratio of acetic acid and acetate at the pK_a of lactic acid can be seen in Figure 15. Punia Bangar *et al.* (2022) reported that lactic acid has the same inhibitory effect as acetic acid on certain species and genera, including *L. monocytogenes*. Additionally, Aguirre-Garcia *et al.* (2024) noted that lactic acid has greater antimicrobial effect on Gram-positive bacteria compared to Gram-negatives. Furthermore, Thylin *et al.* (1995) found that growth of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* (*C. tyrobutyricum*) in silage was inhibited by lactic acid. The study showed that a higher amount of undissociated acid and pH outside of the optima influenced the growth of *C. tyrobutyricum*.

Figure 15. Overview of approximate concentrations of dissociated and undissociated lactic acid at $\text{pH}=\text{pK}_a$.

Citric acid

Citric acid is a tricarboxylic acid meaning it has 3 carboxylic acid groups. Thus, it has 3 pK_a values; 6.40, 4.76 and 3.13 (Mudunkotuwa & Grassian, 2010). This represents the various pH and its level of dissociation as seen in

. According to Punia Bangar *et al.* 2022 citric acid produced by LAB can inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *L. monocytogenes*. A study by Olaimat *et al.* (2017) showed that adding citric acid inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* in diluted tahini but had no inhibitory effect in undiluted tahini. Additionally, the reduction was shown to increase with increasing temperature. This demonstrates the benefit of citric acid as a preservative in uncooled foods with high water activity, such as tahini.

Figure 16. Overview of approximate concentrations at various levels of dissociation of citric acid at $\text{pH}=\text{pK}_a$.

pH=6.40	pH=4.76	pH=3.13
<p>50% Citric acid</p>		
<p>50% Mono-anionic Citrate</p>		

Materials and methods

Fermentations of faba beans and simulated faba bean substrate

In this section the materials and methods for all relevant steps in the experimental setups will be described. All media for streaking, overnight cultures and quantification were made in accordance with the guidelines provided by the producers and the standard procedures of the FOOD section at the University of Copenhagen. All experimental work related to inoculation, fermentation, quantification streaking and creating overnight cultures was conducted in sterile conditions using sterilized equipment and Bunsen burners.

Stock culture preparation

Plates streaked with *L. plantarum* 6-1B, *S. cerevisiae* 36h5cm1 and *B. subtilis* natto were provided by the MiCoP project as seen in Table 1. From these, two overnight cultures were created for each strain. This was carried out by picking up a single colony with a sterile 1 μL loop. The colony was transferred to 10 mL of sterile appropriate broth (see Table 2 for clarification) and incubated at specified temperatures. An overview of the strains as well as corresponding media and incubation temperatures for both agar plate (agar obtained from HiMedia) and broth incubation can be seen in

Table 2

Table 1. Overview of selected strains provided by the MiCoP project, used in fermentation of the FBPC-substrate.

Species and strain	Origin
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> 36h5cm1	Isolated from fura (millet dough), Ghana
<i>L. plantarum</i> 6-1B	Isolated from mawé, Benin
<i>B. subtilis</i> natto	Obtained from commercial “Natto spores” product (LUVI Fermente KG, Lenzing, Austria).

Table 2. Overview of appropriate growth medias and incubation temperatures for the microbial strains used for the FBPC-fermentations.

<i>L. plantarum</i> 6-1B	MRS (Man-Rogosa-Sharpe), HiMedia	30°C shaken at 150 rpm	30°C
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> 36h5cm1	MYGP (Bacto™ Malt extract, Becton and Dickinson, Bacto™ Yeast extract, Gibco, Glucose, Millipore, Peptone, HiMedia)	25°C shaken at 150 rpm	25°C
<i>B. subtilis</i> natto	BHI (Brain Heart Infusion), Himedia	37°C shaken at 225 rpm	30°C
<i>L. plantarum</i> 6-1B	MRS (Man-Rogosa-Sharpe), Himedia	30°C shaken at 150 rpm	30°C

The following day stock cultures were created by vortex mixing the overnight cultures and distributing 600 µL of the cultures into cryotubes before adding 400 µL of a sterile 50% (v/v) glycerol solution prepared from 86% glycerol solution (VWR Chemicals). All stock cultures were stored at -80 °C.

Preparation of inoculum

The inocula was prepared by streaking on appropriate agar plates (as given in Table 2). *L. plantarum* and *S. cerevisiae* were incubated over the weekend while *B. subtilis* natto was streaked

and incubated overnight and consequently stored in the fridge at 4 °C over the weekend (3 days). Overnight cultures were prepared by selecting a single colony from the streaked plates, using a sterile 1 µL loop and following the same procedure as described for the stock culture preparation. Overnight cultures were used to create the inocula the following day. Overnight cultures were transferred to sterile falcon tubes and centrifuged at 4402 × g for 5 min at 20°C in an Eppendorf Centrifuge 5920 R. The supernatant was discarded, and 10.0 mL 0.9 % (w/v) sterile saline solution (NaCl obtained from Sigma Aldrich) was added. The pellet was washed and redispersed by vigorous vortex mixing. Centrifugation and washing were repeated twice. The resulting solution was diluted an appropriate number before measuring an optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀). Due to equipment malfunctions the strains of *L. plantarum* was measured on an LLG-uniSPEC 1 UV/VIS-Spectrophotometer while *B. subtilis* and *S. cerevisiae* were measured on a Thermo Scientific™ GENESYS™ 180 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer. The samples were then diluted to ensure an absorbance below 0.8, where the relationship between CFU/mL and absorbance is linear. Table 3 shows the number of times the various strains were diluted before OD₆₀₀ measurements.

Table 3. Overview of the number of times the various strains were diluted before OD₆₀₀ absorbance measurements.

Strain	Dilution before OD ₆₀₀ measurements
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	x 4
<i>L. plantarum</i>	x 12
<i>B. subtilis</i> natto	x 2

The authors of this thesis did not generate standard curves for the various species, as these were provided by the faculty and can be found in Appendix 1. While the standard curves provided were for different strains than the ones used in this thesis, the growth curves were assumed to be similar enough to use for the inoculation purposes of the fermentation experiments in this thesis. When the microbial suspensions were sufficiently diluted for OD₆₀₀ measurements, the suspensions were vortexed and 1.00 mL were transferred into cuvettes. The spectrophotometer was zeroed against a blank cuvette containing 0.9% sterile saline solution. Standard curves were used to determine the cell concentration (CFU/mL) of the inocula.

Finally, the inocula were adjusted to concentrations of 10^6 CFU/mL and 10^8 CFU/mL for both bacterial species. The inoculum for *S. cerevisiae* was finished after this point, while the inocula for *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis* natto were diluted 10-fold further to a final concentration of 10^7 CFU/mL.

Calculations for the volume of the initial inoculum as well as vol. 0.9% saline solution used to obtain the final concentrations of the inocula are given in Equation 1 and Equation 2.

$$C_{diluted} \cdot V_{diluted} = C_{final} \cdot V_{final} \leftrightarrow V_{diluted} = \frac{C_{final} \cdot V_{final}}{C_{diluted}} \quad [1]$$

Equation 1. Volume of diluted microbial suspension used: where $C_{diluted}$ is the concentration of the washed and diluted overnight culture, $V_{diluted}$ is the volume needed to create the final volume and concentration of the inoculum, C_{final} is the final concentration of the inoculum and V_{final} is the final volume of the inoculum.

$$V_{saline} = V_{final} - V_{diluted} \quad [2]$$

Equation 2. Volume of sterile 0.9 saline solution: where V_{saline} is the amount of 0.9% saline solution needed to obtain the desired final volume V_{final} and $V_{diluted}$ is the volume needed to create the final volume and concentration of the inoculum.

The volumes were pipetted into new sterile falcon tubes. The bacterial cultures were additionally diluted 10-fold as previously described.

Arriving at the final fermentation setup:

Determining the optimal setup for the fermentation experiments was complicated by many factors. Initially, the fermentations were supposed to be carried out on a substrate made from dried raw faba beans. However, this was complicated by contamination of the raw ingredients which prior to the experimental work of this thesis. The contamination was caused by microorganisms that formed heat-resistant spores, which withstood autoclaving at 121°C for 20 min. Superior faculty members sought to arrive at a heat treatment which would eliminate the contamination. This was unfortunately not possible without compromising the nutritional quality of the substrate. For this reason, an alternative substrate consisting of 1% (w/v) sucrose, 1% (w/v) glucose, 7% (w/v) faba bean protein concentrate and deionized water was used to conduct the fermentation experiments as previously described. Henceforth, this substrate will be referred to as FBPC-substrate.

As these experiments progressed it was discovered that the initial stock culture of *B. subtilis* PRO58 was contaminated. All stocks originally created from two separate overnight cultures were contaminated. This may indicate that the original pure-streaked plates provided by the MiCoP project were likely also contaminated. This had also been an issue prior to the work associated with this thesis as communicated by a research assistant working on the MiCoP project. For this reason, the *Bacillus subtilis* fermentations were put on hold for a time.

Furthermore, fermentations using Corning Incorporated® Costar® TC-Treated 3 by 4 well plates were a part of the original setup, to create small and reproducible fermentation experiments using relatively few resources. Plating was done and pH-measurements were carried out at 0, 4, 8, 16, 24 and 48 hrs as depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17 Overview of placement of inoculated wells in duplicate (orange and given by number), controls (green and denoted with C) as well as empty wells (blue and denoted with E) The times are given for 4, 8, 16, 24 and 48 hrs (denoted T4, T8, T16, T24 and T48 respectively).

With this setup control samples were cross contaminated, evident from the macromorphology and colony sizes after quantification (refer to Appendix 2). This issue persisted across all species (*L. plantarum*, *B. subtilis* natto and *S. cerevisiae*) used in the mono-species fermentation experiments. As a result, the substrate was switched to the appropriate broth media for each species (Table 2) to figure out whether the issues arose from the experimental setup or the substrate.

As the issue persisted, two things were thought to be the cause of it; either due to improper handling and sterile technique, or excessive shaking speed of the FBPC-substrate and broths. This may be due to the less viscous nature of these substrates compared to the original substrate made from raw beans. In either case the risk of creating aerosols and causing contamination was too

high in the well-setup. For this reason, the setup was done in 100 mL blue cap bottles with 40 mL broth media and the new time points 0, 6, 24 and 48 hrs were used. Additionally, the technique of the authors was observed by a research assistant of the project to ensure proper sterile practice which was confirmed.

The broth fermentations in 100 mL blue cap bottles were first carried out with *S. cerevisiae* NCYC.625. Two new issues arose. Contamination was observed on several plates with *cocci* (based on micromorphology as seen in Appendix 2. While rigorous preventative methods were employed, the problem persisted. As such, the contamination was thought to come from skin microflora during plate molding rather than the fermentation experiment itself. As such gloves were used during molding as an additional preventative measure to standard sanitation practices.

Furthermore, flocculation of the selected *S. cerevisiae* strain was quite significant (see Appendix 3 for reference). This had not previously been an issue in the well-setup due to the small fermentation volume (2.0 mL). The well-setup allowed for uniform sampling by resuspension of the entire fermentation volume using a pipette. Thus, upscaling of the experiment prevented reproducible sampling from the fermentations to the point where no growth was visible at 24 hrs, but some variable growth was visible at 48 hrs of the fermentation (seen in Appendix 3). For this reason and previous issues with the contaminated *Bacillus* stock, new strains were selected for both *S. cerevisiae* and *B. subtilis* (seen in Table 1). New stock cultures were created for these two strains as described in the, and a final setup was created using 250 mL FBPC-substrate in 500 mL blue cap bottles and will be described in the next section. Dilution rows seen in Table 4 were designed based on previous experiments, where trial and error were used to determine the most suitable dilution range for optimal colony counting in the final setup.

Table 4. Overview of serial dilutions prepared for plating CFU-quantification of each strain in the FBPC-fermentations.

Time (hrs)	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>L. plantarum</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
0	$10^0, 10^{-1}, 10^{-2}$	$10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}$	$10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}$
6	$10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}$	$10^{-2}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-4}$	$10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}$
24	$10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$	$10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$	$10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$
48	$10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$	$10^{-5}, 10^{-6}, 10^{-7}$	$10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$

Final setup of fermentation experiments

Ingredients:

- 17.5 g faba bean protein concentrate, F65X, Vestkorn
- 2.5 g D(+)-Glucose monohydrate, Millipore
- 2.5 g w/v Sucrose (saccharose), Millipore
- 250 mL of ion exchanged water

The day prior to the fermentation experiment the dry ingredients for the substrate were weighed on a laboratory scale and added to a 500 mL blue cap bottle. Ion exchanged water was added by measuring 250 mL in a measuring cylinder. A magnet was added before vigorously stirring until homogenous on a magnetic stirrer and then autoclaved for 20 min at 121 °C. After autoclaving the substrate, it was then placed back on the magnetic stirrer and vigorously stirred overnight.

Each 500 mL blue cap bottle, containing 250 mL of substrate, was inoculated with 2.5 mL of inoculum to achieve an initial concentration of 10^5 CFU/mL for bacteria and 10^3 CFU/mL for yeast. For each strain, two fermentations (biological duplicates) and a negative (uninoculated) control were created as seen in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Overview of the setup using duplicates of 500 mL blue cap bottles inoculated with monocultures of *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis* natto as well as a blind control for each fermentation.

The blue cap bottles containing the fermentations were incubated on a KS 250 Janke & Kunkel IKA Labortechnik orbital shaker at 325 rpm at 30 °C in a heating cabinet with the lids screwed on loosely. The fermentations and controls were removed from the cabinet at each time point (0, 6, 24 and 48 hrs) and mixed on a magnetic stirrer for approximately 1 min. 900.0 µL was then sampled in a sterile Eppendorf tube, which was used to prepare serial dilutions for CFU-count determinations. Dilution rows were prepared using 10-fold serial dilutions, where 100.0 µL of the sample was transferred from the initial Eppendorf tube into a sterile one containing 900.0 µL of sterile 0.9% saline solution, followed by thorough mixing. The process was repeated until an appropriate series was obtained (see Figure 19).

Figure 19. Overview on how the dilution row was created for plating at each time point with a 0.9 saline solution.

For each biological duplicate, three selected dilutions were plated (see Table 4 for details). 100.0 µL of each dilution was pipetted onto MYGP, MRS, and BHI agar plates for *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis* natto, respectively. Dilutions were spread in technical duplicates at each time point using a sterile plastic Drigalski spatula. Due to limited resources, the same Drigalski spatula was used for plating both technical duplicates of each dilution. Before the second plating the Drigalski spatula was briefly held over the flame. Controls were plated on all three media in the same manner but were only plated undiluted and at a 10-fold dilution. Plates were incubated over two days for *L. plantarum* and *S. cerevisiae*, while *B. subtilis* natto was incubated overnight due to rapid proliferation. Colony counting was performed visually within the range of 20–200 colonies. However, for *B. subtilis* natto, the counting area was expanded to 15-200 colonies due to biofilm formation, which significantly reduced reproducibility for dilutions and plating (see Appendix 3).

Between each sample extraction the fermentations and controls were re-incubated as fast as possible. Additionally, 3×4.50 mL was transferred to sterile Falcon tubes for future experiments. A single sample was briefly vortexed and used for measuring pH with a Mettler Toledo FiveEasy F20 pH-meter equipped with a Mettler Toledo InLab® Micro probe. Following this the Falcon tubes stored at -60 °C until further analyses.

Separation and quantification of organic acids and raffinose by HPLC

Sample pretreatment

Organic acid and raffinose concentrations in fermented faba bean samples were determined using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). For HPLC sample preparation, frozen samples collected during fermentations as previously described were thawed for approximately 1 hour. After thawing 1.0 g of faba bean fermentation was added to Falcon tubes and diluted in 5.0 mL of 0.01 M H₂SO₄ (prepared from 95-97% H₂SO₄, Sigma Aldrich) and centrifuged at 4000 × g for 20 min at 4°C in an Eppendorf Centrifuge 5920 R. The supernatant was collected and transferred to new Falcon tubes, then stored at -20°C until further analysis.

Standard and sample preparation

Samples prepared as described in the previous section were thawed at room temperature until fully liquid (~30 min), and 1.0 mL was transferred to HPLC ampules and analyzed internally in the FOOD section at KU.

Standard solutions (10 g/L) of raffinose (prepared from raffinose pentahydrate ≥98.0%, Sigma Aldrich), sucrose (Millipore) and glucose (prepared from D(+)-Glucose monohydrate, Millipore) were prepared alongside organic acid standard solutions (10 g/L) for acetic acid (prepared from 100% acetic acid, Sigma Aldrich), lactic acid (prepared from 85% lactic acid, Sigma Aldrich), and citric acid (prepared from ≥99.5% citric acid, Sigma Aldrich). The standards were first analyzed undiluted to identify the retention times of the organic acids. Only standards for organic acids were then diluted as shown in Table 5 to create calibration curves (Appendix 4) and determine the relationship between concentration and peak area. 1.0 mL diluted standards were transferred to HPLC ampules and analyzed. Additionally, standards solutions of glucose, sucrose and raffinose were measured individually, to distinguish the retention time of raffinose from the sugars added to the FBPC-substrate.

Table 5. Dilution series for organic acid standards. Standard solutions of acetic acid, lactic acid, and citric acid were diluted from a 10 g/L stock to produce calibration curves for quantification by HPLC.

Dilution	Concentration (g/L)
1:5	2.00
1:10	1.00
1:20	0.50
1:40	0.25
1:80	0.13
1:100	0.10
1:1000	0.01

HPLC Analysis

The HPLC analysis was conducted on an Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity II at 35°C, with 5 mM H₂SO (95-97% H₂SO₄, Sigma Aldrich) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min on an Aminex HPX-87H column (300 × 7.8 mm). The HPLC equipment contained a 1200 series quaternary pump (Agilent Technologies), Diode Array Detector (Agilent Technologies) 11000 series set to 210 nm. The setup was equipped with a 1100 series (Agilent Technologies) autosampler, injecting at a volume of 20 µL. Data were evaluated and processed using Agilent ChemStation software (Agilent Technologies).

Data treatment

Peak areas and retention times were collected from the Agilent ChemStation software for all samples and standards. The standards were plotted and used to determine organic acid concentrations. Afterwards, the calculation was adjusted to the weight of the samples as seen in

Equation 3:

$$\frac{c_{\text{supernatant}} \cdot V_{\text{HCl}}}{w_{\text{sample}}} \cdot 1000 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{kg}} \quad [3]$$

Equation 3. Where $c_{\text{supernatant}}$ is the concentration (g/L) of the collected supernatant during extraction, V_{HCl} is the volume (L) of added acid and w_{sample} is the weight (g) of the sample before extraction. 1000g/kg is multiplied for unit conversion from g/g to g/kg.

Where $c_{supernatant}$ is the concentration (g/L) of the collected supernatant during extraction, V_{HCl} is the volume (L) of added acid and w_{sample} is the weight (g) of the sample before extraction. 1000g/kg is multiplied for unit conversion from g/g to g/kg.

Product yield factors Y_{xp} were calculated using Equation 4.

$Y_{xp} = \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta x}$	[4]
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Equation 4. Where Y_{xp} is the product yield factor on cell basis (g/CFU), p is the product concentration (g) and x is the biomass concentration (CFU). Δ indicates the change of a given parameter.

Fermentation and assimilation tests

In this study, raffinose was selected as the sole test substrate for fermentation and assimilation experiments. Although verbascose and stachyose are also members of the RFOs, including these sugars was not possible because their high cost exceeded the project's budget.

Fermentation

12% (w/v) raffinose solution:

- 6 g Raffinose pentahydrate ≥98.0%, Sigma Aldrich
- 50 mL ion exchanged water

Yeast medium for raffinose fermentation:

Ingredients:

- 0.45 g Bacto™ Yeast extract, Thermofisher
- 0.75 g Peptone, HiMedia
- 1.2 mL Bromthymol blue solution
 - 0.021 g Bromthymol blue, Sigma Aldrich
 - 0.53 g 0.1N NaOH, 50% in H₂O, Sigma Aldrich
 - 10 mL ion exchanged water

Bacteria medium for raffinose fermentation:

- API® 50 CHL fermentation medium, Biomérieux
(See Appendix 5 for media composition)

Media preparation

0.50 mL of the yeast fermentation media was dispensed into three test tubes containing Durham tubes and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 min. After cooling, 2.50 mL raffinose solution was added to each tube by sterile filtration as well as to the API® 50 CHL fermentation media. Controls consisted of fermentation media added with 2.50 mL of sterile MilliQ water.

Inoculation and incubation

Before inoculation, MYGP plates were streaked with *S. cerevisiae* 36h5cm1, while BHI and MRS plates were streaked with *B. subtilis* natto and *L. plantarum* 6-1B, respectively. A single colony from each plate was collected using a 5 µL inoculation loop, suspended in 4.5 mL of sterile ion-exchanged water in a Falcon tube, and vortexed to ensure even distribution.

0.1 mL of each suspension was added to the appropriate media and vortexed after inoculation. *S. cerevisiae* was inoculated in the yeast fermentation media, while *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis* natto were inoculated in API® 50 CHL fermentation media. Two experimental samples were prepared along with a (uninoculated) negative control. Tubes inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* were incubated at 25°C for one week, while those containing *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis* natto were incubated at 30°C. Growth was assessed visually every two days based on color changes of the media (see Appendix 5 for visual representation)

Assimilation

Yeast medium for raffinose assimilation:

Ingredients:

- 0.67 g Yeast Nitrogen Base, Difco
- 0.05 g Raffinose pentahydrate ≥98.0%, Sigma Aldrich
- 100 mL MilliQ water

Media preparation

A mixture of 0.5 mL media and 4.5 mL of sterile ion-exchanged water was prepared and distributed into three sterile test tubes. A negative control was prepared in the same manner but without the addition of raffinose.

Inoculation and incubation

Before inoculation, MYGP plates were streaked with *S. cerevisiae* 36h5cm1. A single colony was collected using a 5 µL inoculation loop and suspended in 4.5 mL of sterile ion-exchanged water in a Falcon tube and vortexed to ensure even distribution. 0.1 mL of the suspension was added to the assimilation substrate and incubated at 25°C with shaking at 150 rpm for four weeks. Two experimental samples were prepared along with the negative control and growth was assessed twice a week according to the Wickerham card scoring system.

Phytic acid determination

Phytic acid determination carried out using the Megazyme© phytic acid determination (phytate)/total phosphorous determination kit, which uses enzymatic reactions to release phosphorus. In the assay inorganic phosphate reacts with ammonium molybdate and is then reduced by acidic conditions to molybdenum blue which can be quantified spectrophotometrically at 655 nm. The contents of the kit can be found in

Appendix 6.

Extraction

Prior to the analysis, the frozen samples from FBPC fermentation experiments were freeze-dried at -60°C under 0.04 mbar for 3 days and stored at -60°C prior to the HPLC analysis. The freeze-dried sample was ground with mortar and pestle to a fine powder prior to extractions.

0.249 ± 0.006 g of freeze-dried powder was weighed directly into 100 mL blue cap bottles and the weight was noted. 10.0 mL of 0.66 M HCl (made from 37% HCl, Sigma Aldrich) was added to each bottle, which were all placed on an orbital shaker SSL1, Stuart (142 rpm) for 16 hrs. Extractions were carried out in technical duplicates for all biological replicates obtained from the fermentation. Additionally a duplicate determination was created with oat flour control provided in the kit. The oat controls were included in the analysis, as the total phosphorus concentration was known (0.435% (w/w)), and could be used to adjust for measurement variance.

After extraction 1.0 mL of extract was transferred from each blue cap bottle to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube and centrifuged at 16,200 × g for 10 min. 0.50 mL of the supernatants were transferred to new Eppendorf tubes and 0.50 mL 0.75 M NaOH (made from 50% NaOH solution, Sigma Aldrich) was added to achieve the final neutralized sample. Neutralized samples were stored in the freezer at -20°C until sample preparation for phytic acid determination.

Sample preparation

Each neutralized sample was prepared for spectrophotometric determination of total phosphate and free phosphate. Reagents were shaken and added consecutively to Eppendorf tubes (Table 6).

Table 6. Reagents added for sample preparation of free- and total phosphorus determination in FPBC-substrate fermentation as well as oat-control samples supplied by the Megazyme© phytic acid determination kit, prior to the first incubation of 10 min at 40°C.

Reagent	Volumes for free phosphorus determination (µL)	Volumes for total phosphorous determination (µL)
Deionized water	620	600
Buffer 1, pH 5.5	200	200
Megazyme©		

Neutralized sample extract	50	50
Phytase suspension, Megazyme©	0	20
Total volume a	870	870

After adding the amounts in the order given in Table 6. The Eppendorf tubes were briefly vortexed and incubated in a DB-2D Techne DRI-BLOCK heater at 40°C for 10 min. After this step, reagents given in Table 7 were added consecutively.

Table 7. Reagents added for sample preparation of free- and total phosphorus determination in FPBC-substrate fermentation as well as oat-control samples supplied by the Megazyme© phytic acid determination kit, prior to second round of incubation of 15 min at 40°C.

Reagent	Volumes for free phosphorus determination (µL)	Volumes for total phosphorous determination (µL)
Deionized water	20	0
Buffer 2, pH 10.4, Megazyme©	200	200
Alkaline phosphatase suspension, Megazyme©	0	20
Total volume b	220	220

Afterwards, the samples were incubated in a DB-2D Techne DRI-BLOCK heater at 40°C for 15 min. 300 µL of the 50% TCA reagent (prepared from ≥99.0% trichloroacetic acid, Sigma Aldrich) was added to all tubes and centrifuged at 16,200 × g for 15 min. Meanwhile a color reagent was prepared by adding 1 part of 5% w/v ammonium molybdate solution (prepared from 99.96% ammonium molybdate, Sigma Aldrich) to 5 parts of 10% w/v ascorbic acid solution in 1 M H₂SO₄ (prepared from ≥99.0% L-ascorbic acid, Sigma Aldrich and 95-97% H₂SO₄ solution, Sigma Aldrich). The color reagent was stored at 4°C until usage. Additionally, a standard row of known concentrations of inorganic phosphorous (Table 8) were prepared in Eppendorf tubes.

Table 8. Volumes added for phosphorus standard preparation used in the Megazyme® phytic acid determination.

Standard ID	[P] concentration (µg/mL)	Water volume (µL)	Volume phosphorous standard solution (µL)
STD0	0	1000	0
STD1	0.5	990	10
STD2	2.5	950	50
STD3	5	900	100
STD4	7.5	850	150

After centrifugation 1.0 mL of each sample was transferred to new Eppendorf tubes. 0.50 mL color reagent was added to standards as well as to each sample and oat control (both total and free phosphorus). Finally, the samples, oat controls and standards were vortexed and incubated at 40°C for 1 hour. Sample preparation and analysis were carried out over three rounds, where biological duplicates and one control was included. Due to measurement errors, one sample (*S. cerevisiae* second biological duplicate at 6 hrs of fermentation) was reanalyzed in a subsequent round. After the initial analyses, three additional rounds were conducted to obtain technical replicates.

Measurement

Immediately after incubation, spectrophotometric determination performed with a Thermo Scientific™ GENESYS™ 180 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer. The apparatus was initially set to a fixed wavelength of 655 nm and zeroed against deionized water (1000 µL). 1000 µL of each sample, oat control and standard were filled into cuvettes and measured for determination of free and total phosphorus.

Data treatment

All data treatment was done in accordance with the assay guidelines provided in the Megazyme © kit.

Standard curves

Absorbance (ABS) was corrected by subtracting the absorbance of the standards at 0.0 µg/mL from the measured values of the other standards. Calculations of corrected absorbance are given in Equation 5.

$$ABS_{corr} = ABS_{std} - ABS_{std0} \quad [3]$$

Equation 5. Where ABS_{corr} is the corrected absorbance, ABS_{std} is the absorbance for a point in the standard and ABS_{std0} is the absorbance at 0.0 µg/mL.

According to the protocol, a conversion factor (M) should be calculated as given in Equation 6, rather than using the linear relationship of the standards themselves.

$$M = \frac{c_{Pi} \left(\frac{\mu g}{mL} \right)}{ABS_{corr}} \quad [4]$$

Equation 6. Where M is the conversion factor, c_{Pi} is the concentration of inorganic phosphorus (µg/mL) and ABS_{corr} is the corrected absorbance.

Following this step a mean M of all standards was calculated using Equation 7.

$$M_{mean} = \frac{M_{STD1} + M_{STD2} + M_{STD3} + M_{STD4}}{4} \quad [5]$$

Equation 7. Where M_{mean} is the mean conversion factor and M_{STDn} .

Once the mean conversion factor was determined, data analysis was conducted on the samples and oat controls.

Samples and oat controls

This assay assumes that any phosphorus in the sample not accounted for as free phosphorus originates from phytic acid. For this reason, the first step of the data treatment is to subtract the absorbance of the free phosphorous determination from the absorbance of the total phosphorous determination as seen in Equation 8.

$$\Delta ABS = ABS_{total} - ABS_{free} \quad [6]$$

Equation 8. Where ABS_{total} is the absorbance of total phosphorus determination for a given sample and ABS_{free} is the absorbance of free phosphorus determination for the same sample.

Additionally, the dilution factor during sample preparation was determined with Equation 9 where the dilution factor for neutralization of the extract and the dilution factor for further dilution during the assay is calculated and multiplied with one another.

$$F_{dilution} = \frac{V_{neutralized}}{V_{acid}} \cdot \frac{V_{total(a)} \cdot V_{total(b)} \cdot V_{TCA}}{V_{sample}} \quad [7]$$

Equation 9. Where $F_{dilution}$ is the dilution factor, $V_{neutralized}$ is the volume of a neutralized sample, V_{acid} is the volume of HCl, V_a is the total volume a (given in Table 6), V_b is the total volume b (given in Table 7). V_{TCA} is the volume of TCA and V_{sample} is the volume of sample.

Please note that the color reagent is not included in this calculation, because the concentration is assumed to be known in the standards even after addition (same amount added for standards as well as samples).

The sample concentration in g/100 g was determined using Equation 10:

$$\Delta c_{Pi} = \frac{M_{mean} \cdot V_{extract} \cdot F_{dilution}}{10,000 \cdot w_{sample} \cdot V_{assay}} \cdot \Delta ABS \quad [8]$$

Equation 10. Where c_{Pi} is the concentration of inorganic phosphate, M_{mean} is the mean conversion factor, $F_{dilution}$ is the dilution factor, w_{sample} is the weight of the samples and oat controls, V_{assay} is the volume of sample used for colorimetric determination in the assay (without the color reagent) and ΔABS is the difference in absorbance between total and free phosphate of a sample.

Finally, an additional conversion factor was used to calculate the amount of phytic acid which is comprised of 28.2% phosphorus according to the Megazyme© phytic acid determination kit. This calculation is mathematically expressed in Equation 11:

$$c_{phyt} = \frac{\Delta c_{Pi}}{0.282} \quad [9]$$

Equation 11. Where c_{phyt} is the phytate concentration of a sample, Δc_{Pi} is the difference of concentration between free and total phosphorous and 0.282 is a conversion factor for phytate.

Vicine and convicine determination

A standard for vicine and convicine could not be created due to their cost. For this reason, the data was treated as relative values (%). Additionally, the number of samples analyzed had to be limited to 20 samples out of a total of 36, due the expense of the analysis itself. Consequently, the control samples were all excluded except for two at 0 hrs of fermentation. This was based on the assumption that controls would show no change in the concentration of vicine and convicine throughout the incubation period of the FBPC fermentation experiments. Furthermore, only 2 samples of inoculated fermentations collected at 0 hrs of fermentation were analyzed. A bacterial

sample (*B. subtilis* natto) and a yeast sample (*S. cerevisiae*) was selected at 0 hrs of fermentation. For *B. subtilis* samples, the 6-hr time points of this fermentation were excluded as the metabolic activity of the species were assumed to be minimal due to growth inhibition. An overview of the sample selection for the analysis can be found in Table 9.

Table 9. Overview of the samples included (green and x) and excluded (red and -) for the vicine and convicine determination using LC-MS. #1 denotes replicate number 1, #2 denotes replicate number 2 and #3 denotes replicate number 3 used in the FBPC-substrate fermentations.

Time (hrs)	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>		<i>L. plantarum</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i> natto		Controls		
	#1	#2	#1	#2	#1	#2	#1	#2	#3
0	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	-	x
6	x	x	x	x	-	-	-	-	-
24	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	-
48	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	-

Extraction

Prior to the analysis, the frozen samples (as shown in Table 9) from previous FBPC fermentation experiments were freeze-dried and grounded.

51.2 ± 1.3 mg freeze dried sample was weighed into 2 mL Eppendorf tubes. The weights were noted and 500 µL extraction solution with uridine consisting of 70:30, acetone:water and 2 mM uridine (prepared from ≥99.9% acetone, deionized water and ≥99% uridine) was added to each sample. The samples were subsequently vortexed for approximately 10 seconds. Due to the lack of a suitable overhead shaker, the samples were secured to the back of a Roto-Shake Genie™, Scientific Industries Inc. and operated at a setting of 35 rpm. After 30 min the samples were centrifuged at 16,200 × g for 30 mins. 300 µL of the supernatants were transferred to new 1.5 Eppendorf tubes. 500 µL extraction solution 70:30, acetone:water without uridine (prepared from ≥99.9% acetone and deionized water) was added to each sample. The samples were vigorously vortexed until redispersed and subsequently placed back on the Roto-Shake Genie™ at 35 rpm for 30 min. Finally, the samples were centrifugated at 16,200 × g and 400 µL was extracted from the supernatants and pooled into the previously extracted supernatant of each sample. After this step the final extract was achieved, and the samples were stored at -20°C until measurement.

Sample preparation

The sample preparation was conducted by the DynaMo MS-Analytics Facility at the Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences at the University of Copenhagen. For this reason specific brands for chemicals used, preparation of solutions as well as equipment and brands are unknown.

Thawed samples were diluted 50 times by adding 980 μL 90% acetonitrile (LC-MS grade) solution to 20 μL of the final extract. The samples were then centrifuged at $13,000 \times g$ for 5 min at 4 °C.

Following centrifugation, 25 μL of the supernatants was further diluted in 975 μL of 90% acetonitrile solution. Samples were then ready for measurement.

Measurement

LC-MS was carried out with a Waters BEH amide column (2.1 \times 100 mm, 1.8 μm) at 40 °C. Each sample was injected at 5 μL to mobile phase. The mobile phase was pumped through the column at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. Furthermore, the mobile phase had a gradient of two mobile phases; Mobile phase A (10 mM ammonium acetate and 0.1% formic acid in water) and Mobile phase B (10mM ammonium acetate and 0.1% formic acid in 90% acetonitrile solution). The concentrations of each of the mobile phases at different time points are provided in Table 10.

Table 10. Concentrations of mobile phase A and B at different time points, which was used for vicine and convicine determination using LC-MS.

Time (min)	Mobile phase A (%)	Mobile phase (B) (%)
0.0	0	100
0.2	0	100
0.7	5	95
4.1	30	70
4.2	0	100
6.0	0	100

Data treatment

For the data analysis, the samples were normalized for comparability between collected samples, relative to the uridine concentration using Equation 12.

$$peak_{norm} = \frac{\left(\frac{peak_p}{peak_u}\right)}{w_{sample}} \quad [10]$$

Equation 12. Where $peak_{norm}$ is the normalized peak area of either vicine or convicine, $peak_p$ is LC-MS peaks for the either vicine or convicine, $peak_u$ is the corresponding LC-MS peak for uridine and w_{sample} is the weight of the sample.

Finally, the concentration (%) at each time point was calculated as a relative measure between the average peak area for each sample across biological replicates and the average normalized peak area for all samples collected **0 hrs of fermentation**, as described in Equation 13. This resulted in a single reference value, derived from all LC-MS data collected and analyzed at the start of fermentation.

$$c_{\%} = \frac{AVG_{peak_{norm_x}}}{AVG_{peak_{norm_{t0}}} \cdot 100 \quad [11]$$

Equation 13. Where $c_{\%}$ is the relative concentration in percent, $AVG_{peak_{norm_x}}$ is the average peak between biological replicates or samples collected at 0 hrs of fermentation and $AVG_{peak_{norm_{t0}}}$ is the average of all normalized peaks collected at 0 hrs of fermentation.

Statistics and general data treatment

General data treatment:

Averages were calculated using the Excel function; AVERAGE(), which uses the equation given in Equation 14.

$$\mu = \frac{\sum x_i}{N} \quad [14]$$

Equation 14. Where x_i is each individual value in the dataset, N is the number of samples and μ is the average value.

Standard deviations were calculated using the Excel function; STDEV.P(), which uses the equation given in Equation 15

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x_i - \mu)^2}{N}} \quad [15]$$

Equation 15. Where x_i is each individual value in the dataset, N is the number of samples and μ is the average value and σ is the standard deviation.

Additionally, statistical significance was assessed with a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). This was carried out for for phytic, acetic, lactic and citric acid determination as well as pH measurements during fermentations. Due to a data point exclusion from control 3 on citric acid measurements as well as the inability of Excel to create ANOVA on unevenly distributed and missing data, control 3 was excluded from the model.

When significant variance between groups (species and controls) used in the fermentation experiments, time and/or interaction was observed, post-hoc 2-tailed T-test, assuming uneven variance was used to confirm significant differences. 2-tailed T-test was employed because the interest is in significant difference, not whether the difference is an increase or a decrease. Additionally, the assumption of uneven variance was to avoid false positives due to relatively large variation among replicates.

Results and discussion

FBPC-substrate fermentations

The growth of each microorganism as well as the pH of the FBPC-substrate blue-cap fermentations were monitored 0, 6, 24 and 48 hrs of fermentation.

Microbial growth assessment in FBPC-substrate fermentations

The initial cell density of *S. cerevisiae* (Figure 20) reached an average concentration $(1.08 \pm 0.22) \times 10^4$ CFU/mL, which is a tenfold higher than the concentration of 1.00×10^3 CFU/mL that was aimed for in terms of the inoculation concentration of yeast cells. This may be due to the standard curve used to predict cell count in *S. cerevisiae* 36h5cm1, was based on the growth on a different strain of *S. cerevisiae*. After reaching a population exceeding 1.00×10^8 CFU/mL during exponential growth (6-24 hrs), the cell density stabilized after 24 hrs of fermentation, indicating entry into the stationary phase. This suggests efficient utilization of available sugars in the FBPC-substrate, consistent with the fermentative capabilities in various substrates reported by Feldmann 2012. A final cell population of $(1.64 \pm 0.08) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL was reached after 48 hrs of fermentation.

L. plantarum had an initial cell concentration of $(1.54 \pm 0.00) \times 10^5$ CFU/mL (Figure 20), closely aligning with the desired concentration of 1.00×10^5 CFU/mL for bacterial cells. Similar to *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum* exhibited exponential growth between 6-24 hrs of fermentation, approaching a concentration of 1.00×10^9 CFU/mL. The stationary growth phase of *L. plantarum* began after 24 hrs of fermentation, reaching a final cell concentration of $(7.75 \pm 0.25) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL after 48 hrs of incubation. Similar results were reported by Rosa-Sibakov *et al.* (2018), who observed a final cell count of approximately 1.00×10^8 CFU/mL after 24 hrs of fermentation when inoculating with approximately 1.00×10^6 CFU/mL. A single technical replicate from a biological duplicate of *L. plantarum* had observed contamination at 48 hrs of fermentation. Since samples were technical replicates obtained from the same blue cap bottle, it is likely that the contamination originated from the agar plate. Consequently, the sample was not excluded for pH measurements. Additionally, it should be noted that out of 12 control agar plates (4 BHI, 4 MRS, and 4 MYGP) used at each time point, only a single BHI plate showed contamination at 0 hrs, and one MRS plate at 6 hrs of fermentation. As the contamination did not persist in technical duplicates, the plate was assumed to be the source. The contaminated control plates and the

contaminated MRS plate for quantification of *L. plantarum* at 48 hrs of fermentation were excluded.

The average initial cell concentration for *B. subtilis* natto was $(4.05 \pm 0.40) \times 10^4$ CFU/mL (Figure 20) which is lower than the concentration of 1.00×10^5 CFU/mL that was aimed for. In contrast to the growth dynamics of *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum*, *B. subtilis* natto duplicates displayed a ten-fold decrease in cell density within the first 6 hrs of fermentation, indicating growth inhibition at the start of the fermentation. The cause of the apparent growth inhibition is unexplained.

Adaptation of *B. subtilis* natto to the FBPC-substrate or possible limited oxygen availability would not explain the decrease in viable cell count that was observed in early fermentation (0-6 hrs).

Further investigation is needed to determine the exact cause. The growth inhibition of *B. subtilis* natto was followed by an exponential increase in cell count that occurred within 6-48 hrs of fermentation. *B. subtilis* natto did not appear to reach a stationary growth phase during the fermentation period, as no plateau can be observed on the growth curve (Figure 20). At the end of the fermentation the cell population of *B. subtilis* natto reached an average concentration of $(2.00 \pm 0.25) \times 10^6$ CFU/mL, which is substantially lower than the cell concentration of *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum*. None of the growth curves for the microorganisms displayed a lag-phase as well as a classic sigmoidal trend. This may be due to insufficient sampling frequency in the experimental design resulting in a less comprehensive representation of the growth dynamics.

Figure 20. Growth curves for *S. cerevisiae* (yellow), *L. plantarum* (blue) and *b. subtilis natto* (green) inoculated and incubated in FBPC-substrate over 48 hrs at 30°C.

pH-changes during fermentation of FBPC-substrate

For pH the ANOVA model results showed very low p-values (<0.001) for groups (various species and controls), measured time points and interactions signifying a less than 0.1% chance of random occurrence. With post hoc Welch T-test this was confirmed for the pH measured at 24 and 48 hrs of fermentation for *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* (p-values<0.05). Additionally, the pH determination for *B. subtilis natto* at 48 hrs of fermentation proved significant (p-values<0.05).

Table d. Overview of ANOVA model results for pH, where SS is the sum of squares, df is degrees of freedom, MS is the mean sum of squares, F is the F-value and P-value represents the significance level. Group denotes species used for fermentation and controls while time denotes the time of sampling. Interaction denotes the interaction between Groups and Time and Residual indicates the residual error.

ANOVA model for lactic acid concentration					
Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Group	3.27	3	1.09	875.50	<0.001
Time	4.41	3	1.47	1178.49	<0.001
Interaction	3.46	9	0.38	308.73	<0.001
Residual	0.02	16	0.00	-	-

The initial pH of samples from *S. cerevisiae* fermentation and the controls was measured to 6.07 ± 0.02 and 6.03 ± 0.04 , respectively. Samples inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* displayed a steep initial drop in pH in the interval 6-24 hrs of fermentation (Figure 21), indicating substrate acidification, likely driven by organic acid production during sugar metabolism. Afterwards, the pH reached a minimum of 5.25 ± 0.00 . This was followed by a slight increase in pH to 5.30 ± 0.01 after 48 hrs, indicating a stabilization in pH at the end of fermentation. In contrast, the controls remained more stable over time, though they displayed a minor decline in pH between 24-48 hrs, reaching a final pH of 5.92 ± 0.02 after 48 hrs of fermentation (Figure 21). This minor decrease in the controls implies that more substantial acidification in the inoculated samples was mainly driven by microbial activity rather than spontaneous changes in the substrate.

The pH at the start of the fermentation in *L. plantarum* samples was measured to 6.02 ± 0.02 . Similar to *S. cerevisiae*, samples inoculated with *L. plantarum* displayed a steep initial drop in pH within 6-24 hrs of fermentation (Figure 21), but as opposed to *S. cerevisiae* fermentations, the pH appeared to decrease gradually throughout the entire fermentation period, reaching a final minimum pH of 4.05 ± 0.00 , comparable to results from Kahala *et al.* (2023). Thus, indicating a greater acidification of the substrate, compared to the acidification capabilities of *S. cerevisiae*. The continuous pH decline suggests considerable organic acid production, likely lactic acid, which is characteristic of LAB metabolism (Corsetti & Valmorri 2011). This ongoing acidification indicates that nutrient availability remained sufficient to support continuous acid production, even during

stationary growth, in *L. plantarum* fermentations. By effectively lowering the pH of the FBPC substrate, *L. plantarum* inhibits a range of spoilage organisms and pathogens, enhancing the safety and shelf life of fermented products (Corsetti & Valmorri 2011). This makes it a strong candidate for fermenting faba bean products to improve shelf-life stability.

In *B. subtilis* natto fermentations, the initial pH was measured to 6.09 ± 0.00 and remained relatively stable over the 48-hour period (Figure 21), showing only a slight decline compared to the controls. Minimal pH reduction was observed within the first 24 hrs, suggesting limited acid production during early fermentation. However, between 24 and 48 hrs, the pH decreased to 5.56 ± 0.02 , indicating a metabolic shift leading to mild acidification. This differs from the *L. plantarum* fermentations, which exhibited a significant pH drop in the same time interval. The mild acidification in *B. subtilis* natto fermentations may indicate lower organic acid production or the production of weaker acids. This could also be due to a preference for other metabolic pathways, such as proteolysis, rather than carbohydrate utilization. Additionally, ammonia released during proteolysis can react with acids, partially neutralizing them. When present in sufficient amounts, ammonia can not only reduce acidification but also elevate pH. In other legume-based fermentations, *Bacillus* species have been shown to contribute to alkalization driven by proteolysis (Parkouda *et al.* 2009).

Figure 21. pH development in FBPC-substrate fermentations inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* (yellow), *L. plantarum* (blue) and *B. subtilis natto* (green).

Raffinose and organic acid content

Raffinose could not be separated and quantified in the fermentation samples by HPLC analysis, as no peak matching the expected retention time of 7.54 min (*Appendix 4*) was detected. This may be due to low concentrations or limitations in the method. Further method optimization may be needed for accurate extraction and detection. Additionally, one sample (control sample 3 from 24 hrs of incubation of the FBPC-substrate) was excluded from the HPLC analysis, as it exhibited outlier behavior, as the peak area of citric acid deviated from the other two replicates due to improper peak integration by the ChemStation software (see *Appendix 4* for details). This improper integration may have occurred because the citric acid peak appears as a shoulder on a larger peak. Peaks for acetic, citric and lactic acid were determined at the retention times 17.59 ± 0.02 , 9.08 ± 0.00 and 14431.86 ± 3.72 min respectively and the overall concentrations measured for organic acid concentrations can be seen in Table 11.

Table 11. Organic acid concentrations (g/kg) in faba bean substrate during fermentation with S. cerevisiae, L. plantarum, and B. subtilis natto over 48 hrs. Concentrations of acetic acid, lactic acid, and citric acid were determined by HPLC at 0, 6, 24, and 48 hrs. Values represent means \pm SD of two determinations (n = 2).

Organic acid	Treatment	0 hrs (g/kg)	6 hrs (g/kg)	24 hrs (g/kg)	48 hrs (g/kg)
Acetic acid	Control	0.86 ± 0.00	0.79 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.02
	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	0.84 ± 0.00	0.78 ± 0.06	1.78 ± 0.26	0.35 ± 0.02
	<i>L. plantarum</i>	0.84 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.01	0.82 ± 0.01	1.17 ± 0.04
	<i>B. subtilis</i> natto	0.88 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.04	1.42 ± 0.09	2.41 ± 0.29
Citric acid	Control	1.01 ± 0.10	0.93 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.01	1.02 ± 0.10
	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	1.06 ± 0.23	0.92 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.05
	<i>L. plantarum</i>	0.93 ± 0.23	0.91 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.02	1.08 ± 0.05
	<i>B. subtilis</i> natto	0.96 ± 0.23	0.92 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.05
lactic acid	Control	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00
	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.00
	<i>L. plantarum</i>	0.05 ± 0.00	0.06 ± 0.00	2.88 ± 0.16	5.04 ± 0.01
	<i>B. subtilis</i> natto	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00	0.05 ± 0.00	0.28 ± 0.14

Results obtained from the two-way model with repetitions on acetic acid concentration can be seen in Table 12. Both groups (microorganisms and controls) as well as time of sample collection and interaction between the two groups have a p-value < 0.001 . This indicates a very low likelihood of random occurrence ($< 0.1\%$).

Post-hoc Welch T-test confirmed the significance of levels of acetic acid for *B. subtilis* natto at 24 hrs of fermentation (p-value=0.041). However, the acetic acid levels for *B. subtilis* natto at 48 hrs of fermentation was not significantly different from controls (p-value=0.055). Similarly, the increase in acetic acid concentration at 24 hrs for *S. cerevisiae* fermentations was not shown to be significant (p-value=0.081), while the decrease at 48 hrs was significant (p-value=0.009). This can be explained by the statistical power of variance. These two data points have a higher variation between determinations for the biological duplicates (Figure 22), which influences the confidence of the T-test. The p-values suggest that the acetic acid concentrations for *S. cerevisiae* and *B. subtilis* natto at 48 hrs have a 5.5% and 8.1% probability, respectively, of occurring by random chance. Thus, due to limited data (biological duplicates) which may cause higher variance, these results could be attributed to Type II errors (false negatives). As such the T-test might have failed to detect a significant variation even if one exists.

Table 12. Overview of ANOVA model results for acetic acid concentration, where SS is the sum of squares, df is degrees of freedom, MS is the mean sum of squares, F is the F-value and P-value represents the significance level. Group denotes species used for fermentation and controls while time denotes the time of sampling. Interaction denotes the interaction between Groups and Time and Residual indicates the residual error.

ANOVA model for acetic acid concentration					
Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Group	1.46	3	0.49	91.99	<0.001
Time	1.22	3	0.41	76.79	<0.001
Interaction	4.54	9	0.50	95.46	<0.001
Residual	0.08	16	0.01	-	-

In terms of acetic acid production in *L. plantarum* fermentations, acetic acid remained relatively stable for the first 24 hrs (0.84 ± 0.02 to 0.82 ± 0.01) before increasing to 1.17 ± 0.04 g/kg at 48 hrs of fermentation (**Fejl! Henvisningskilde ikke fundet.**), indicating increased acetic acid production in the later stages of fermentation. Acetic acid concentration in *B. subtilis* natto fermentations significantly increased to 1.42 ± 0.09 g/kg and accumulated the highest concentration (2.41 ± 0.29 g/kg) after 48 hrs. Conversely, the acetic acid concentration peaked for *S. cerevisiae* at 24 hrs (1.78 ± 0.26 g/kg) before declining significantly to 0.35 ± 0.02 g/kg. This decline suggests acetic acid consumption due to glucose depletion between 24 and 48 hrs, which only produced slight elevation in pH seen in Figure 21. This is likely due to the presence of other acids. Furthermore,

the decline in acetic acid concentration after 48 hrs of fermentation could imply that sufficient oxygen is present in the media for the yeast to metabolize two-carbon sources such as acetic acid through the glyoxylate cycle. This likely means that sugars are sparse in the FBPC-substrate at 48 hrs of fermentation which would be in accordance with Feldmann (2012) and Palma *et al.* (2018).

Figure 22. Average acetic acid concentration in fermentations with *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis natto* over 48 hrs. Measurements were taken at 0, 6, 24, and 48 hrs. Error bars represent standard deviations.

Results from the two-way model with repetitions on citric concentration can be seen in Table 13. Both groups (microorganisms and controls) as well as time of sample collection and interaction between the two groups have a p-value <0.05.

Post hoc Welch T-test revealed that the decrease in citric acid content in fermentations with *S. cerevisiae* was significantly different from controls (p=0.001). The further decrease observed at 48 hrs of fermentation for this species was however insignificant (p=0.103). This was also the case for *B. subtilis natto* at 48 hrs of fermentation (p=0.216). As can be seen in Figure 23, the data collected for 48 hrs of fermentation generally have higher variance between measurements compared to

measurements taken for 24 hrs of fermentation. This again produces a likelihood for a type II error, possibly due to the limited amount of data produced by biological duplicates. This means that a significant difference might exist but could be undetectable through T-test.

Table 13. Overview of ANOVA model results for citric acid concentration, where SS is the sum of squares, df is degrees of freedom, MS is the mean sum of squares, F is the F-value and P-value represents the significance level. Group denotes species used for fermentation and controls while time denotes the time of sampling. Interaction denotes the interaction between Groups and Time and Residual indicates the residual error.

ANOVA model for lactic acid concentration					
Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Group	0.25	3	0.08	4.91	0.013
Time	0.38	3	0.13	7.61	0.002
Interaction	0.43	9	0.05	2.90	0.031
Residual	0.02	16	0.00	-	-

Like acetic acid, citric acid was consumed by *S. cerevisiae*, decreasing significantly from an initial concentration of 1.06 ± 0.23 g/kg to 0.58 ± 0.02 g/kg at 24 hrs of fermentation (Figure 23). This was followed by a further decrease to 0.52 ± 0.05 at 24 and 48 hrs of fermentation. Similarly, the initial concentration of 0.96 ± 0.23 g/kg for *B. subtilis* natto remained relatively stable and comparable to controls before dropping to 0.69 ± 0.05 g/kg at 48 hrs of fermentation. In contrast, citric acid levels in *L. plantarum* fermentations followed controls throughout the duration of the fermentation, indicating limited citrate metabolism of this particular strain.

Figure 23. Average citric acid concentration in fermentations with *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis natto* over 48 hrs. Measurements were taken at 0, 6, 24, and 48 hrs. Error bars represent standard deviations.

Results of the two-way ANOVA model with repetitions on lactic concentration can be seen in Table 14. Both groups (various microorganisms and controls) as well as time of sample collection and interaction between the two groups have a p-value <0.001. This indicates a very low likelihood of random occurrence (< 0.1%).

Through Welch T-test the lactic acid concentration for fermentations with *L. plantarum* at 24 and 48 hrs of fermentation was deemed significantly different from controls with p-values of 0.018 and 0.001 respectively. No other lactic acid concentrations varied significantly from controls.

Table 14. Overview of ANOVA model results for lactic acid concentration, where SS is the sum of squares, df is degrees of freedom, MS is the mean sum of squares, F is the F-value and P-value represents the significance level. Group denotes species used for fermentation and controls while time denotes the time of sampling. Interaction denotes the interaction between Groups and Time and Residual indicates the residual error.

ANOVA model for lactic acid concentration					
Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Group	22.63	3	7.54	5216.31	<0.001
Time	9.49	3	3.16	2187.39	<0.001
Interaction	25.77	9	2.86	1980.34	<0.001
Residual	0.02	16	0.00	-	-

L. plantarum was the most efficient lactic acid producer across species (Figure 24). The initial concentration increased significantly from 0.05 ± 0.00 g/kg to 2.88 ± 0.16 g/kg and 5.04 ± 0.01 g/kg after 24 and 48 hrs, respectively (Figure 24). Conversely, *S. cerevisiae* maintained a stable concentration, following the tendency of the controls throughout the duration of the fermentation. *B. subtilis* natto showed no change from the initial concentration in lactic acid of 0.05 ± 0.00 g/kg until 48 hrs, where an increase to 0.28 ± 0.14 g/kg was observed. However, this final concentration remained lower than in *L. plantarum* fermentations, indicating that *B. subtilis* natto is not an avid lactic acid producer. The limited acidification observed in *B. subtilis* natto samples further supports this, as its pH decline was less pronounced compared to *L. plantarum* (Figure 21).

Figure 24. Average lactic acid concentration in fermentations with *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis natto* over 48 hrs. Measurements were taken at 0, 6, 24, and 48 hrs. Error bars represent standard deviations

In terms of the antimicrobial effect, the organic acids produced by *B. subtilis natto* did not correspond to a significant pH reduction (Figure 21). This suggests that the acids are far from their pK_a values, meaning they mainly exist in their undissociated form, thus diminishing their antimicrobial effect. *S. cerevisiae* demonstrated a significant decrease in pH in the exponential phase (Figure 21). HPLC analysis revealed that although pH was maintained until the end of fermentation, acetic acid had been consumed to a significant degree at 48 hrs of fermentation (Figure 22). Furthermore, *S. cerevisiae* did not appear to produce citric and lactic acid, which may indicate the production of other organic acids lowering pH regardless (Figure 21). Additionally, the *S. cerevisiae* apparent switch to diauxie might suggest the consumption of other antimicrobial compounds such as ethanol. However, this is outside the scope of this thesis. Finally, *L. plantarum* accumulated acetic acid after 48 hrs of fermentation and produced significantly high

concentrations of lactic acid at both 24 and 48 hrs. Additionally, fermentation with *L. plantarum* resulted in the most stable trend in citrate concentration as well as the lowest pH observed during fermentations.

In Table 5 the product yield factors (cell basis) at the highest accumulated concentrations for *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* fermentations can be seen. *B. subtilis* natto was not included as it never reached a stationary growth phase (Figure 20). The accumulation of acetic acid per cell is highest for *S. cerevisiae* at 24 hours of fermentation, yielding a product yield factor of $(7.00 \pm 0.44) \cdot 10^{-9}$ [g/CFU]. This is substantially higher than any product yield factor determined for *L. plantarum*, including both acetic acid $(0.46 \pm 0.05) \cdot 10^{-9}$ [g/CFU] and lactic acid $(2.79 \pm 0.19) \cdot 10^{-9}$ [g/CFU]. This was seen despite no production of lactic acid was observed for *S. cerevisiae*. This means that *S. cerevisiae* is the most effective acid producer overall. However, this does not mean that *S. cerevisiae* fermentations achieved a higher concentration of acid, as *L. plantarum* reached almost a 10-fold higher cell population. Additionally, acetic acid has a lower pK_a , meaning it is a weaker acid compared to lactic acid and thus less efficient at lowering pH (Figure 21). These findings suggest that *L. plantarum* is more suited than *S. cerevisiae* and *B. subtilis* natto for improving shelf-life stability in faba bean matrices through organic acid production. While *L. plantarum* is not the most efficient acid producer, it produced the highest concentration of organic acid as well as yielding the lowest pH in the FBPC-substrate fermentations. Notably, after 48 hrs of fermentation it appears that *S. cerevisiae* enters diauxie, thus consuming and consequently reducing the antimicrobial effect of acetic acid and possibly ethanol.

Table 15. Overview over product yield factors for acetic and lactic acids at maximum concentrations measured during the stationary phase of *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum*.

	Species	Time of fermentation (hours)	Product yield at maximum organic acid concentration · 10⁻⁹ (g/CFU)
Acetic acid	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	24	7.00 ± 0.44
	<i>L. plantarum</i>	48	0.46 ± 0.05
Lactic acid	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	24	0.00 ± 0.00
	<i>L. plantarum</i>	48	2.79 ± 0.19

Fermentation and assimilation of RFOs

To evaluate the ability of *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis* natto to metabolize raffinose, fermentation and assimilation tests were conducted. Fermentation was assessed by monitoring CO₂ production, while assimilation was determined based on microbial growth. Additionally, pH was measured for *B. subtilis* natto at the end of the experiment. The following results provide insight into the metabolic activity of each microorganism, with raffinose as the sole carbon source.

Table 16. Results from fermentation and assimilation tests using raffinose as the sole carbon source.

Microorganism	Strain	Assimilation of raffinose	Fermentation of raffinose
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	36h5cm1	-	+
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	6-1B	N/A	+
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	natto	Inconclusive	Inconclusive

As shown in Table 16, both *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* demonstrated the ability to ferment raffinose. In tubes inoculated with *S. cerevisiae*, CO₂ production showed fermentative behavior, confirming findings from Romero-Espinoza *et al.* (2020) and Kasproicz-Potcka *et al.* (2018). Similarly, a pH-induced color change in tubes inoculated with *L. plantarum* confirms its fermentative activity as well as its role in reduction of RFOs, in agreement with findings from Kitum *et al.* (2020) and Paventi *et al.* (2024). In contrast, *B. subtilis* natto showed no color change but exhibited surface ring formation and turbid growth in both replicates (Appendix). To assess whether *B. subtilis* natto fermented raffinose into organic acids and consequently lowered the pH, pH measurements were conducted. However, the results showed an increase in pH, suggesting proteolytic activity rather than raffinose fermentation (Table 17). This indicates metabolic activity and growth, likely driven by the utilization of nitrogen sources in the medium.

Table 17. pH measurements of *B. subtilis* natto fermentation tests.

Sample	pH
Control	6.96
<i>B. subtilis</i> natto #1	8.92
<i>B. subtilis</i> natto #2	9.13

Assimilation tests indicated that *S. cerevisiae* was unable to assimilate raffinose. While raffinose assimilation is not uncommon among *S. cerevisiae* (Hayford & Jespersen 1999), these findings are not unlikely as previous studies have reported strain variations in terms of raffinose assimilation in *S. cerevisiae* (van der Aa Kühle *et al.* 2001). While *B. subtilis* natto displayed growth in the substrate, the inconclusive fermentation test may suggest that it might utilize raffinose for growth and could potentially assimilate it as a carbon source. However, since the medium was formulated for *Lactobacillus* species, further testing with a minimal medium optimized for *Bacilli* is recommended. Due to the strong proteolytic activity of *B. subtilis*, its growth may have been supported by protein sources in the medium. Additional testing in a minimal medium designed specifically for *Bacillus* could provide a better assessment of its ability to assimilate raffinose.

The results of the fermentation and assimilation tests provide insight into the metabolic capabilities of *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis* natto when raffinose is used as the sole carbon source. The findings confirm that both *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* are capable of fermenting raffinose, as indicated by CO₂ production and pH reduction, respectively. These observations align with previous studies (Romero-Espinoza *et al.* 2020; Kasproicz-Potocka *et al.* 2018; Azeke *et al.* 2005; Paventi *et al.* 2024), which have reported similar fermentation patterns for these microorganisms. The ability of *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* to ferment raffinose suggests their possible use in optimizing the digestibility of faba beans, in terms of RFO degradation.

On the contrary, *B. subtilis* natto did not exhibit clear signs of raffinose fermentation, as no significant pH reduction was observed. Instead, an average pH increase of 29.67% was measured, suggesting release of ammonia through proteolytic activity rather than carbohydrate fermentation thus increasing pH. This aligns with the known metabolic characteristics of *Bacillus* species, which are capable of utilizing nitrogen-rich compounds as alternative energy sources (Parkouda *et al.* 2009). While growth was observed in tubes inoculated with *B. subtilis* natto, it is unclear whether raffinose was directly assimilated. The observed growth could be attributed to the presence of polypeptone and yeast extract in the API[®] 50 CHL medium (see Appendix 5 for media composition), which *B. subtilis* natto may have metabolized instead of raffinose.

This thesis aimed to assess the ability of *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*, and *B. subtilis* natto to degrade RFOs. However, due to budget constraints, only raffinose was tested. Verbascose and stachyose are more structurally complex than raffinose because they contain additional galactose units. As a result, excluding these sugars limits how well the findings can be applied to all RFOs. According to the literature, microbial metabolism of RFOs is often driven by α -galactosidase activity, which breaks down terminal galactose residues. While previous studies suggest that microorganisms capable of metabolizing raffinose can also utilize other RFOs (Kitum *et al.* 2020) the results may differ due to the increased complexity of verbascose and stachyose, enzyme specificity as well as variances between strains. Although the findings in this section indicate that *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* can utilize raffinose as a carbon source, this does not necessarily mean they can break down these longer-chain RFOs containing α -(1,6) bonds between galactose units (Figure 6). Thus, metabolization of raffinose does not automatically mean equally effective degradation of stachyose and verbascose.

Phytic acid determination

First the standards were plotted to ensure linearity as can be seen in Appendix 6.

The phytic acid concentration over time in the fermentations and controls are given in Figure 25. At 0 hrs of fermentation, the average measurement across species and controls was 1.48 ± 0.04 g/g dry matter, showing minimal variation between samples. The controls remain relatively consistent over time. Bacterial fermentations for *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis* natto showed a decrease in phytic acid concentration at 6 hrs followed by a further decline at 24 hrs of fermentation, reaching 1.37 ± 0.10 g/g dry matter and 1.24 ± 0.2 g/g dry matter, respectively. Curiously, an increase in phytic acid concentration is seen at 48 hrs for both bacterial fermentations, reaching a final concentration of 1.56 ± 0.02 g/g dry matter for *L. plantarum* and 1.40 ± 0.06 g/g dry matter for *B. subtilis* natto.

An initial decrease to 1.32 ± 0.05 g/g dry matter at 6 hrs of fermentation is seen for *S. cerevisiae*. Remarkably, at 24 hrs of fermentation, a substantial increase to 1.79 ± 0.03 g/g dry matter is seen for the yeast fermentation, which remains consistent at 48 hrs of fermentation with only a slight further increase to 1.86 ± 0.04 g/g dry matter. Notably the standard deviation for *S. cerevisiae* at 24 hrs and 48 hrs of fermentation is relatively small. Additionally, it appears the variation between

measurements increases towards the 24-hour mark for the bacterial samples and the controls. A slight decrease in the variation is seen after 48 hrs of fermentation.

Figure 25. Phytic acid concentration (g/g dry matter) in FPBC-substrates inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* (yellow), *L. plantarum* (blue), *B. subtilis natto* (green) as well as controls (hatched red).

Results obtained from the two-way model with repetitions on phytic acid concentration can be seen in Table 18. The table shows a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) within groups (microorganisms and controls) as well as between timepoints of fermentation measured. Notably, the interaction between the two reduces the significance ($p > 0.05$), however the p-value for interactions is bordering the significance ($p = 0.0513$). This suggests that the effect of the factors are co-dependent. For this reason and differences in variances between groups, post-hoc T-tests of the various fermentations did not determine any significant differences between controls and fermentations. Additionally, it should be noted that the ANOVA model takes all data into account and determines if one group is significantly different from another, while the T-test only compares specific time points. As such, the T-test often yields a higher p-value compared to the ANOVA model in general.

Table 18. Overview of ANOVA model results for acetic acid concentration, where SS is the sum of squares, df is degrees of freedom, MS is the mean sum of squares, F is the F-value and P-value represents the significance level. Group denotes species used for ferm

ANOVA model for phytic acid concentration					
Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Group	0.23	3	0.08	4.78	0.0146
Time	0.17	3	0.06	3.52	0.0392
Interaction	0.37	9	0.04	2.52	0.0513
Residual	0.26	16	0.02		

However, the apparent consistent increase in phytic acid concentration for *S. cerevisiae* fermentations at 2h and 48 hrs of fermentation is unexpected. However, considering the findings in literature (Wang & Guo, 2021; Wang et al. 2018; Selle et al. 2012) suggesting that interactions between phytic acid and proteins can be induced by heat treatment for some proteins, this could be a possible explanation. If the phytic acid becomes entrapped in substrate protein aggregates after autoclaving, enzymatic access could be affected. This could potentially lead to an underestimation of the total phosphorus level in the early phases of the fermentation (0 and 6 hrs of fermentation) since phytase and alkaline phosphatase are used in the determination method. If this is the case, even a small amount of proteolytic activity, might loosen and break up aggregates later in the fermentation (24 and 48 hrs of fermentation), which may make the phytic acid more accessible to enzymatic degradation. Since strain variance in phytic acid utilization by *S. cerevisiae* is high (Mikulski & Kłosowski 2017), it is possible that the strain used in this study has a low rate of utilization which might explain the increase in phytic acid concentration in the substrate. This could mean that *S. cerevisiae* might release phytic acid from protein aggregates without further degrading the phytic acid. Furthermore, this could also suggest that similar mechanisms could make any phytic acid degradation by *B. subtilis* natto and *L. plantarum* less apparent if they were to release and degrade phytic acid simultaneously, obscuring any changes in concentration.

Reevaluating the FBPC fermentation setup to improve the reproducibility of technical replicates may be beneficial. Additionally, steps should be taken to ensure that phosphorus determination is accurate and reliable.

Vicine and convicine determination

Peaks for uridine, vicine and convicine were determined at the retention times 0.83 ± 0.017 , 2.21 ± 0.00376 and 2.33 ± 0.0555 min, respectively.

In Figure 26, the relative concentration (%) of vicine is given for each species over time. In *S. cerevisiae* fermentations, vicine concentration increases rapidly from the initial collective concentration of $100.0 \pm 5.6\%$ between 6 and 24 hrs of fermentation, reaching an average concentration of $132.3 \pm 2.7\%$ at 24 hrs across biological duplicates.

For the yeast fermentation only a slight further increase to $132.6 \pm 1.6\%$ is seen at 48 hrs of fermentation. For *L. plantarum* fermentations, only a small increase in vicine concentration of $103.7 \pm 1.2\%$ at 6 hrs of fermentation occurs, followed by a slight increase to $104.8 \pm 1.6\%$ at 24 hrs. At 48 hrs of fermentation the trend returns to the baseline, reaching a concentration of $99.5 \pm 1.8\%$. For *B. subtilis* natto fermentations, the vicine concentration remains relatively stable, but a shift to a lower concentration of $96.9 \pm 11\%$ can be observed at 24 hrs of fermentation. At 48 hrs of fermentation, the trend returns to baseline reaching a concentration of $99.7 \pm 5.9\%$.

Figure 26. Relative vicine concentration (%) in FBPC-substrate inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* (yellow), *L. plantarum* (blue) and *B. subtilis natto* (green).

For convicine determination similar trends can be seen in Figure 27. The initial collective concentration (%) starts at $100.0 \pm 4.4\%$. Similarly to the trend for vicine concentration, *S. cerevisiae* fermentations show a rapid increase in the relative convicine concentration between 6 and 24 hrs of fermentation from $103.5 \pm 1.5\%$ to $133.2 \pm 7.5\%$, respectively. Thereafter the concentration slightly drops to $128.2 \pm 1.4\%$ at 48 hrs of fermentation. Also, for *L. plantarum* fermentations an increase is seen between 6 and 24 hrs reaching a concentration of $115.9 \pm 3.1\%$. This decrease in the relative convicine concentration is more substantial than that of vicine for this species. At 48 hrs of fermentation the concentration decreases again to a concentration of $103.1 \pm 0.4\%$. *B. subtilis natto* fermentations the relative convicine concentration remains somewhat stable with only small variations to $98.9 \pm 6.3\%$ and $101.3 \pm 3.1\%$ at 24 and 48 hrs of fermentation, respectively.

Figure 27. Relative convicine concentration (%) in FBPC-substrate inoculated with *S. cerevisiae* (yellow), *L. plantarum* (blue) and *B. subtilis natto* (green).

Due to the sample limitation for LC-MS, statistical analysis cannot be performed on progressions of the relative vicine and convicine concentration. This is caused by an insufficient time resolved overview of the FBPC-substrate fermentations. Any statistical analysis would likely overestimate the relevance due to missing control measurements over time. However, an increase can be noted between 6 and 24 hrs for *S. cerevisiae* fermentations for both vicine and convicine. This increase appears to be maintained at 48 hrs as well and cannot be attributed to changes in solubility of vicine and convicine as this is pH dependent. This is due to the solubility of vicine and convicine increases at acidic and alkaline pH, respectively (Rizzello *et al.* 2016; Bangar & Dhull 2022). This does not correspond with Figure a and Figure b, as levels of vicine and convicine appear to increase for *S. cerevisiae* fermentations. Additionally, these increases appear to correlate with the rise in phytic acid concentrations observed at the same time points (Figure 25). As these analyses were extracted separately and performed by different people, human error may not have been the cause of the similar trends in concentrations of phytic, vicine and convicine.

Additionally, some findings in literature suggests interactions with macro-nutritional components and phytic acid during heat treatment, no such literature has been found for vicine and convicine. In summary, these results remain inconclusive due to the lack of a reasonable explanation and the inability to determine statistical significance.

Conclusion

This thesis investigated the potential of fermenting faba bean protein concentrates (FBPC) with selected microorganisms (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, and *Bacillus subtilis*) to enhance nutritional value by reducing anti-nutritional factors and improving shelf-life stability through organic acid production.

The study demonstrated that *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* can successfully grow in faba bean matrices, reaching final cell concentrations of $(1.64 \pm 0.08) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL and $(7.75 \pm 0.25) \times 10^8$ CFU/mL, respectively, after 48 hours of fermentation. In contrast, *B. subtilis* natto showed limited growth, with its cell concentration reaching only $(2.00 \pm 0.25) \times 10^6$ CFU/mL, due to growth inhibition during early fermentation.

The results also highlighted variations in organic acid production among the microbial species. While *S. cerevisiae* was shown to be the most effective organic acid producer, it later metabolized acetic acid, which limited its ability a lower pH beyond a minimum pH of 5.25 ± 0.00 during the fermentation period. In contrast, *L. plantarum* produced substantial amounts of lactic acid, reducing the pH to 4.05 ± 0.00 after 48 hours, which may help extend shelf life by inhibiting microbial spoilage.

Both *L. plantarum* and *S. cerevisiae* exhibited the ability to ferment raffinose, indicating a potential reduction in its content within faba bean matrices. However, this does not necessarily imply that they can break down more complex raffinose family oligosaccharides. Additionally, the role of *B. subtilis* natto in relation to raffinose fermentation remains unclear, as the results were inconclusive. Additionally, fermentation of FBPC did not significantly reduce phytic acid, vicine, or convicine concentrations. Notably, in *S. cerevisiae*, these compounds even appeared to increase during the stationary phase. As the substrate investigated in this thesis is based on a protein concentrate rather than raw faba beans, findings may not apply to the latter.

Future perspectives

The findings of this thesis contribute to the understanding of how fermentation with selected microorganisms affects the production of organic acids and the degradation of antinutrients in faba bean matrices. Although the results indicate the potential microbial fermentation has as a sustainable approach to improving nutritional value and enhancing microbial shelf-life stability in faba bean protein concentrates, further research is needed to confirm and expand on these findings as well as address limitations and challenges that occurred in this thesis.

Future research could include optimization of the fermentation setup and parameters. This study used specific strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, and *Bacillus subtilis*, but further work could investigate the influence of other microbial strains, co-culturing, and fermentation conditions, such as temperature, pH, and fermentation time. Additionally, investigating sequential fermentation may enhance the effectiveness of antinutrient degradation.

Future studies should also explore whether the fermentation and assimilation tendency that was observed for raffinose also apply to verbascose and stachyose, as their complexity may affect microbial metabolism and their role in improving faba bean digestibility. Investigation of how different microorganisms interact with these oligosaccharides could aid in optimizing fermentation approaches for maximizing nutrient bioavailability.

Additionally, several limitations in the experimental setup should be considered in future research. These include considering that composition of the simulated faba bean substrate, differs from unprocessed faba beans in terms of protein functionality as well as macro- and micronutrient interactions. For example, protein interactions with phytic acid may have influenced the results of phytic acid determination. To overcome this issue, future studies using the simulated media could enzymatically digest samples before analysis to improve measurement reliability. Such as using unspecific proteases to investigate whether protein aggregation may have entrapped acid, causing measurement variation.

Another potential issue is the fermentation setup, where only a total of 13.5 mL (3×4.5 mL) was removed for sampling, from the total fermentation volume of 250 mL. This limited sample volume may affect the statistical power of the results and how well they represent the entire system. Additionally, for phytic acid determination, only small amounts of freeze-dried sample

(approximately 0.25 g) were available for analysis. A possible solution to overcome this could be to do smaller fermentations in separate bottles for each time point. This way the entire system could be collected at each sampling point and frozen after CFU quantification, allowing for a larger sample size for analyses.

Moreover, to ensure reliability and reproducibility, future studies should aim to increase the number of biological and technical replicates or each analysis as well as fermentations, to increase statistical reliability in the findings. This would aid in reducing variability as well as allow for more advanced statistical analyses, such as principal component analysis (PCA) and other multivariate analysis tools, to better interpret trends and relationships within the data.

Furthermore, while shelf-life was discussed in this thesis, no analyses were performed to quantitatively or qualitatively assess it. Future research could therefore include shelf-life studies to evaluate microbial stability.

Lastly, future studies should determine whether the observed benefits of fermentation are exclusive to faba bean protein concentrates or if they can be applied to whole faba beans. Additionally, combining fermentation with other processing techniques, such as enzymatic pretreatment, germination, etc., may further improve the nutritional value of faba beans.

In conclusion, while this study provides insights into the effects of fermentation on faba bean protein concentrates, there are various areas that future research can optimize and expand upon, and thereby contribute to developing sustainable, nutritious, and functional plant-based foods.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Standard curves used for OD₆₀₀-determinations of *S. cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum* and *B. subtilis*.

Appendix 2

Pictures of observed contamination during the fermentation experiments

Figure 28. A. MRS plate streaked with *L. plantarum* 6-1B. B. MRS plate streaked with uninoculated FBPC-substrate, displaying signs of cross contamination from *L. plantarum* 6-1B.

Figure 29. Phase contrast microscopy image of contamination, hypothesized to be cocci on plates used for CFU quantification in FBPC-substrate fermentation.

Appendix 3

Growth assessment of microorganisms used for FBPC-substrate fermentations

Assessment of B. subtilis natto during 24 and 48 hrs of fermentation

Figure 30. BHI plates inoculated with various dilutions of FBPC-substrate fermented with *B. subtilis natto* at 24 (A.) and 48 hrs of fermentation (B.).

Figure 31 chain and biofilm formation of *B. subtilis natto* at 100x phase contrast microscopy.

Assessment of *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625

Figure 32. Picture of the flocculating behavior of *S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625 in MYGP broth.

Figure 33. Phase contrast microscopy images of flocculating yeast cells (*S. cerevisiae* NCYC 625) at 100x magnification.

Appendix 4

HPLC-chromatograms

HPLC chromatograms of sugars

Figure 34. Chromatogram of raffinose (10 g/L) measured by HPLC.

Figure 35. Chromatogram of sucrose (10 g/L) measured by HPLC.

Figure 36. Chromatogram of glucose (10 g/L) measured by HPLC.

HPLC chromatograms of FBPC-substrate fermentations
 FBPC-substrate fermentation controls

Figure 37. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate control sample no. 1 after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 38. Figure 23. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate control sample no. 2 after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 39. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate control sample no. 3 after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 40. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate control sample no. 1 after 24h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 41. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate control sample no. 2 after 24h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 42. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate control sample no. 3 after 24h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

FBPC-substrate fermentation with *S. cerevisiae*

Figure 43. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate fermented with *S. cerevisiae* (sample no. 1) after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 44. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate fermented with *S. cerevisiae* (sample no. 2) after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

FBPC-substrate fermentation with *L. plantarum*

Figure 45. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate fermented with *L. plantarum* (sample no. 1) after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 46. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate fermented with *L. plantarum* (sample no. 2) after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

FBPC-substrate fermentation with *B. subtilis* natto

Figure 47. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate fermented with *B. subtilis* natto (sample no. 1) after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

Figure 48. Chromatogram of FBPC-substrate fermented with *B. subtilis* natto (sample no. 2) after 0h fermentation, measured by HPLC.

HPLC organic acid standard calibration curves

Acetic acid standard calibration curve

Lactic acid standard calibration curve

Citric acid standard calibration curve

Appendix 5

Assimilation and fermentation tests

Wickerham scoring system

+	Positive 2+ or 3+ on Wickerham card after 1 week
1	Delayed positive 2+ or 2+ on Wickerham card after 2 weeks
w	Weak positive 1+ on Wickerham card
-	Negative No growth

Pictures from raffinose fermentation and assimilation tests

Figure 49. Bacterial fermentation tests in API® 50 CHL medium after 4 days of incubation at 30°C with shaking at 200 rpm. Control (yellow), *Bacillus subtilis* natto (red) and *L. plantarum* (blue).

API® 50 CHL medium composition

COMPOSITION OF THE MEDIUM

API 50 CHL Medium 10 ml	Polypeptone	10 g
	(bovine/porcine origin)	
	Yeast extract	5 g
	Tween 80	1 ml
	Dipotassium phosphate	2 g
	Sodium acetate	5 g
	Diammonium citrate	2 g
	Magnesium sulfate	0.20 g
	Manganese sulfate	0.05 g
	Bromcresol purple	0.17 g
	Demineralized water	1000 ml
pH : 6.7-7.1		

Figure 50. Cut-out of the API® 50 CHL medium composition from Biomer.

Appendix 6

Phytic acid determination

Megazyme kit contents for phytic acid determination

Kit contents:

- Buffer 1 (pH 5.5)
- Phytase suspension
- Buffer 2 (pH 10.4)
- Alkaline phosphatase suspension
- Phosphorous standard solution (50 µg/mL)
- Oat flour control (0.435% w/w total phosphorous)

All liquid solutions were shaken before use.

Additional solutions made:

- 0.66 M HCL solution stored at room temperature
- 0.75 M NaOH solution stored at room temperature
- 50% w/v TCA solution stored at 4°C for no longer than 6 months
- 10% w/v Ascorbic acid solution in 1 M H₂SO₄ stored at 4°C for no longer than 1 week
- 5% w/v ammonium molybdate solution stored at 4°C for no longer than 1 month

KITS:

Kits suitable for performing 50 assays are available from Megazyme. The kits contain the full assay method plus:

- Bottle 1:** Buffer (25 mL, pH 5.5) and sodium azide (0.02% w/v) as a preservative.
Stable for > 2 years at 4°C.
- Bottle 2:** Phytase suspension (1.2 mL).
Stable for > 2 years at 4°C.
- Bottle 3:** Buffer (25 mL, pH 10.4), plus MgCl₂, ZnSO₄ and sodium azide (0.02% w/v) as a preservative.
Stable for > 2 years at 4°C.
- Bottle 4:** Alkaline phosphatase suspension (1.2 mL).
Stable for > 2 years at 4°C.
- Bottle 5:** Phosphorus standard solution (24 mL, 50 µg/mL) and sodium azide (0.02% w/v) as a preservative.
Stable for > 2 years at 4°C.
- Bottle 6:** Oat flour control powder (5 g, Phosphorus content, see bottle).
Stable for > 5 years at room temperature.

Standard curves used for phytic acid determination

